

DID JESUS STUDY VEDANTA ?

A paper made possible through an open minded modern examination of the history of Jesus found in India, Kashmir, Afghanistan, Persia, Turkey, Syria and Palestine; and produced by an author who was baptised in the UK as a Christian in 1944.

This paper examines how the teaching of Jesus became a victim of a phenomenon called **Euro-centrism**; the intense desire and habit of telling other people how to live their lives.

It also shows that Jesus actually gained the insights which he displayed in Palestine from an area of the planet which had been a very advanced civilisation. An advanced people who, arising from a deep insight into human life, had progressed or evolved away from the primitive desire to control the lives of others.

In that ancient culture they had learned to understand the psychology of human life to a very advanced degree. They had full knowledge of the rebirth of the human soul and the progress which can be made over many embodiments as a human being.

This knowledge enabled them to have a relaxed approach to the subject of belief in a Creator of the universe. Knowing that human beings not only need a long time to become fully knowledgeable about that subject, but that they would keep any progress made and take it to their next embodiment to build on it.

With all this advanced knowledge, they had no need for a desire to control the spiritual life of others.

Leaving each to work on their own individual progress at their own pace. A method which Jesus learned but the Jews of Jesus' time did not know; and were not willing to embrace in their lives; the same applies to the modern so called Christian church.

EUROCENTRICISM

So that this paper can be more truly appreciated I wish to introduce readers to a concept which I will call **Eurocentricism**. This is maybe a new word for many, so I need to explain what is meant by it. In my other papers readers will see that, although I was born and educated in England (UK), I have travelled and absorbed the ancient culture of non-European peoples; viz. Pythagorean Sufism and Indian philosophy. This travel to far away countries was not for academic reasons, but for personal interest in the culture of those places visited. Also I went to those places to study under accomplished masters of the various subjects that I was deeply interested in. Hence in my papers there has been an awakening of this subject of Eurocentricism; meaning that these countries have suffered from impositions which have been introduced or forced onto their culture from European type people and mentioned to me by those masters when teaching me. This information I have dutifully passed on in my other papers.

In my view much of this whole world has become subjected to ideas coming from people who have originated from Europe. So much of the whole world is now suffering from Eurocentricism. These Europeans began their promulgation during times when a fanatic false form of Christianity was gripping them. Hence their fanatic false ideas of their belief system were forced onto other cultures. Later, many of these European countries have given up their fanatic approach to their beliefs; but unfortunately the damage is done, and those other countries, worldwide, are still suffering the effects and have hung on to the fanaticism.

In subsequent centuries this has been followed with the Eurocentric dominance of scientific theories, many of which are also false, in that the unproved theories are taught in schools as if they are fact. Add to this the highly mutable nature of digital ways of living and it now it looks like the world will be ruined due to these things spreading into the lives of all people; taking away their freedom to think and act for themselves in line with their traditional cultures; and giving them weapons and other technology which they never could have produced themselves. Let alone the criminal and other harmful activities through digital means, which they could not have easily derived by themselves.

Yet if we go back to the times when Jesus was living on this planet, Britain was nothing, America was nothing and most of Europe was troubled with barbaric, generally uncivilised, tribes of people beating the brains out of each other, stealing each others valuables and women. These European people, who gradually became more organised and a little more civilised, achieved this due to a few good ideas which were spoken by Jesus. A tiny fraction of his knowledge and philosophy changed a whole continent. Where did Jesus learn to speak in such a way? Few people who have belonged to fanatic religious sects have asked this question. If they had really understood Jesus' teachings they would have dropped their centuries old primitive habit of wanting to make or tell other people (or nations) how to live their lives, now called Eurocentricism.

It is not yet a century since Europeans stopped fighting each other. Yet they have not stopped trying to impose their ideas onto other nations. This imposition is coming from all those types whose ancestry originates in Europe, whichever continent they currently live on. They brought the habit, of telling others what to do, with them to their country and have never stopped it nor have they controlled it; or even realised that it is there. This is what I mean by global Eurocentricism. Europeans do not realise what they have been responsible for.

However, more than two thousand years before Jesus' time there was high civilisation in both China and India. These areas were the centre of the world in terms of technology and knowledge of how to live a noble life. Yet then as now these cultures do not have the habit of telling other cultures how to live their lives. Before Jesus' time middle eastern peoples looked further East for trade, trinkets, teaching and technology. In the city of Taxila (near the modern Afghan - Pakistan border) there was a university which taught all subjects to a high degree. The Harappan civilisation in the Indus valley had architecturally planned cities with organised streets, and drainage systems. They had a sophisticated waste disposal system. Each house had a proper toilet and bathing room. The sewage went through a system of drains getting bigger as they collected the waste to convey it onto agricultural fields for fertilisation. They made building bricks with amazing accuracy and had many technologies relating to pottery, metal smelting, fine jewellery and other manufacturing techniques. All these along with a sophisticated weights and measures system.

All this advancement thousands of years before Europeans and peoples of the Middle East started to become civilised. Other evidence shows that the Harappans of the Indus valley were also living by the ancient knowledge of the Vedas and much of the culture they had then has continued into the present day.¹ Their knowledge and ways have survived thousands of years, without the need to tell anyone that they must also live by it; and much longer lasting than this temporary destructive digital electronic fashion might be.

It was into the area of the Indus valley that Jesus went to find a connection with that ancient teaching. Contrary to the way Eurocentricism has promoted his teaching, it did in fact come from the Indus valley and associated areas. A land where the people of Jesus' time knew to go to get more advanced things which they were not capable of producing. It was where he learned to understand human psychology and how to avoid, or progress beyond, the need to force people or tell them how they must live their lives. Instead he showed the options available and left people to choose the appropriate way for themselves. Hold the above in mind as you read the rest of this paper. It may change your view of the old Eurocentric story told about Jesus, his life and teachings.

And you may consider that old Eurocentric view to now be obsolete.

¹ The Harappan Civilization by Tarini Carr - Archaeology Online

INTRODUCTION

Traditionally we know that Jesus lived in both Egypt and Judaea during the first decade or longer of his younger years. We also know that he returned to Palestine later in life to try and teach people in the area of his youth, knowledge which he had gained during those, apparently unrecorded, years in-between. The New Testament gives clear evidence that he survived, in some way, the attempt to execute him through crucifixion; since there are several reports of him meeting and eating with his followers after that event. The spin about resurrection and subsequent ascension was not the teaching of Jesus, but statements made by others who did not all witness what was written.² These were based on outdated spurious Jewish theories of both the soul and resurrection; and their mistaken idea that heaven is a physical place in the sky. Spirits or ghosts have no need to eat food; also there is no tomb with Jesus' remains in it in the Palestine area. Human bodies cannot vanish into thin air; so where did he go?

Hence, the field is really left open for Jesus to have had more years of his life both studying and teaching in areas outside of Palestine. This includes years before he returned to Palestine and after he left there in his forties. The fact that this has been proved and recorded in historical accounts of his life was refused by earlier Christians (and still is today by traditionalists) on the basis that it would upset their theories that he allowed ignorant barbarians to kill him and later consider him to be a sacrificial animal in the blood-for-sins trade.

The above ideas and theories do not originate in the minds of those who hold fast to them. They were formed by fanatic Romans who wanted to use religious ideas to dominate the lives of Europeans; after their attempts to dominate through militaristic methods had finally failed. Hence thereafter the Roman Empire became re-titled as the Holy Roman Empire, the seeds of Eurocentricism. It was this HRE which indelibly impregnated its ideas onto all Europeans enforced by the Roman Inquisition. This many centuries long interrogation of the thinking of all people in Europe, was enacted through burning all people who held other ideas not in accordance with the so called church. This mainly promoted the idea that Jesus was killed and his death turned out to be a good thing as all others would be saved by it. This Eurocentric false doctrine has spread worldwide. It started with the Roman military rule of Europe and has never really gone away. The same idea of control is happening in this 21st century through European Community domination of the lives and cultures of all European Community member countries.

² I once spoke to a policeman taking his case into a court of law. He said although he had eight witnesses to the incident, all witness statements were so different from each other, it was as if they were all different incidents. He was not certain that he could win his case. Yet all eight witnesses signed a statement of being truthful.

The Christians believe that the purpose of the supposed death of Jesus was to subsequently redeem the sins of people he had never met. This idea was created by a man from Anatolia (Turkey) who was employed to persecute the Jewish followers of Jesus. It was not a concept recorded or proposed in the documents of Jesus' teachings (the Gospels). Later the Pagan Emperor Constantine adopted the non-pagan teachings of others and forced his new idea of a religion onto all the squabbling factions of his empire.³ After that this invented religion became called Christianity. The above is recorded history which anyone can verify for themselves.

Perhaps it is a little audacious to describe the early history of the Christian belief system in the above way. But it is more than likely nearer to the truth of the situation of religious belief in early European history, than most so called modern Christians are likely to want to accept. Sometimes when the truth upsets long term held falsity, this does have a disturbing effect on the hearer. But the once established Roman Inquisition has officially expired for just over a century, so it is safer for us to think for ourselves with little risk of being burnt on a wooden stake. Also we can hold ideas which the traditional Christians have not yet given themselves the freedom to do. Perhaps they have not yet realised that the extraordinary powers given to earlier so called Christian leaders through the Inquisition courts, are not applicable in this free thinking 21st century.

There is no concept whatever in Jesus' teaching that dissenters should be murdered by burning. The woman who was propose to be stoned to death as a result of her sexual behaviour, was in fact pardoned by Jesus and given his best advice to make her life better.⁴ (John Chpt. 8 vv 3-11)

Here I have outlined the nature of this paper which seeks to apply doctorate scholarship to the subjects of who Jesus was, the kind of man he was and how he came by those revolutionary ideas which the Jews and other people of his time could neither understand nor accept.

First let us demolish some of the fake news which has taken over Christian thought for nearly two thousand years; promoted through the century by century growing wave of Eurocentricism. This may leave the way clear for the possibility that Jesus' teachings originated from the Ancient System of Righteousness currently still taught in parts of India and embodied within Vedanta. A system which has stayed the same for thousands of years longer than anything that Eurocentrics have devised and forced onto others.

³ Taken from "The Biography of Jesus" a limited private publication. Contact - saraswati.soc@btinternet.com

⁴ The Gospel of John 8:3 to 11 "Neither do I condemn you." (for having committed adultery).

DEATH BY CRUCIFIXION

Contrary to some ideas, crucifixion was not always meant to be a death sentence. History shows that death when fixed to a tree or cross would not occur until the person's body had been hanging there for more than three or four days.⁵ It is for this reason that the Inquisition courts approved of a fire to be lit under the body so that death would occur much sooner. It was not practical to guard dozens of bodies tied or fixed to wooden stakes for several days; and without guards the victims could easily be freed alive by family, friends or associates. So the fire was the method. If death was the sentence, then there have always been more certain methods than merely fixing and suspending the body to a wooden stake or cross.

This is the first item of fake news which the people of Palestine were apparently subjected to. It is known that Jesus was put on the cross on a Friday afternoon and that the Holy Sabbath of the Jews begins on sunset on Fridays. The Jews never allowed bodies to be left on a cross on their Holy Sabbath day. So Jesus was removed from the cross on the Friday evening. Hence is it not possible for Jesus to have died from being on that cross for only a few hours. But Jesus was a magical and capable wise man and would have been easily able to fake death. It is reported that Jesus walked on water (Matt. 14:24 & 25). For this he used a power called **laghima** in Sanskrit; a mystic power to reduce the weight of the body to zero (i.e. levitation). He would have used this on the cross also; so that his body would not suffer. The New Testament records that Joseph of Aramathea, a previously unmentioned disciple of Jesus, (Matthew 27:57) asked for possession of the body from Pilate. The New Testament states that, "and Pilate marvelled if he were already dead" (Mark 15:44). In our context saying, "Surely he cannot be dead already." But he gave the body to Joseph and not, as would have been normal, to his accuser the Jewish High Priest. This speaks of Pilate's sympathy with the plan of Jesus.

The fake news of Jesus' death would have been acceptable to Jesus and his associates at the time. The whole crucifixion and death report was quite clearly part of a plan by Jesus and his secret circle of followers.⁶ We need to view the crucifixion with open eyes about the kind of powers which Jesus was reported to have had. These were magical powers that few Christians know of and many Christians do not believe in.⁷ It would have been easy for such a powerful man to enact an illusory scene for those that were gullible enough to believe it.

⁵ See - "Jesus Died in Kashmir" by Gordon and Cremonesi - page 26. Also the erudite article by Dr. Stroud in the Spectator dated 10th April 1847 page 16; where he eliminates all possibility that Jesus could have died on the cross.; and states, "The immediate cause of Christ's death has yet to be sought." i.e. he could not have died.

⁶ See the chapter "The Arrest and Execution" told by Ellias in "The Biography of Jesus" a limited private publication. Contact - saraswati.soc@btinternet.com

⁷ See Appendix 2 "The Siddhi or Mystical powers" in the above book "The Biography of Jesus".

So here we have a new way of viewing the reported crucifixion, which can easily be shown to demolish the false long held idea promoted by the Romans. It does not matter how convincing the old story is; no truly honest person would wish to hold onto a story when later evidence shows it to be fabricated.

If after many years the conviction of a man for a murder is shown to have been based on false or inconclusive evidence, would an honest and just person still commit that man to a death sentence? Do not Christians wish themselves to be considered as honest and just people? This question they need to answer to themselves as individuals and to no other.

ABSOLUTION THROUGH BLOOD SACRIFICE

In the letters of Saul of Tarsus he writes, (my comments in brackets).

"Now when these things were thus ordained, the priest went always into the first tabernacle accomplishing the service of God.

"But into the second went the high priest alone once every year, not without blood, which he offered for himself and for the errors of the people." (Hebrews. 9: 6 - 7)

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"For when Moses had spoken every precept to all the people (the Jews) according to the law, he took the blood of calves and of goats, with water, and scarlet wool and hyssop, and sprinkled both the book and all the people,"

"Saying, 'This is the blood of the testament which God hath enjoined unto you.'

"Moreover he sprinkled with blood both the tabernacle and all the vessels of the ministry.

"And almost all things are by the law (of Judaism) purged with blood; and without shedding of blood is no remission (of sins)."
(Hebrews. 9: 19 - 22)

This was the tradition which he imbibed from childhood. A belief that killing a goat or a calf would free people from their sins if the blood of the slaughtered animal was sprinkled during a ceremony. So how could such a strange idea have taken hold of a whole nation of people? It is recorded history that ancient people, perhaps prior to the establishment of the Jewish tribes, really believed that killing their own first born child as an offering to their gods, would bring them some favour from such gods. Perhaps the favour of a life free from punishment arising from their misdemeanours. This must have been a very strong idea if it convinced a human being, with some intelligence, to give up attachment to a baby child and to take its life so as to satisfy a belief. The word "sacrifice" meant originally to "make sacred". Its meaning has been altered to mean this religious idea of killing or giving up something precious. There is nothing sacred in killing an innocent creature.

It is recorded in the scriptures of the Jews that one of their ancestors called Abraham found a way to finally quash this ancient tradition by substituting a goat for his own son at the time of the sacrifice. There would have been no need for that episode in Genesis Chpt. 22 if there had not been some Jewish tribes who still had a belief in the above mentioned sacrifice of a first born child. It was necessary to make an attempt to put to bed this barbaric idea of child sacrifice. Hence a scenario is written for the benefit of those who might not have accepted the sacrifice of the goat or lamb as being sufficient.

In whatever way that scripture is written we should simply understand that the writers of it put their own spin on an incident; where Abraham clearly saw that taking an innocent human life was unacceptable to an awakened person such as he was; one who would wish no violence on any creature, let alone his own first born child. So the scripture, written by a human, attributes the change in tradition to the voice of their god. This change was surely a welcome relief to the mothers who must have suffered great anguish at the death of a baby that they had gone through so much pain to bring alive into the world; and loved so much. So Abraham kick started a new idea of never using human blood for the remission of sin.

The killing of innocent animals to satisfy a human belief, however much it was misguided, had continued for many centuries before Saul of Tarsus wrote the above words. Whatever their belief in the cleansing potential of blood sacrifice it is clear that Saul did not believe in it. Or at least we could say that it did not work for him. He wanted to start his own Jewish sect; and part of the doctrine of that new sect would be the idea of human blood sacrifice used for redemption. This was to replace the defunct system of animal sacrifice which many Jews were possibly tired of repeating every year. Hence he writes :-

"But Christ being come an high priest of good things to come, by a greater and more perfect tabernacle, not made with hands, that is to say, not of this building.

"Neither by the blood of goats and calves, but by his own blood he entered in once (for all time) into the holy place, having obtained eternal redemption for us (a longer lasting redemption.)

"For if the blood of bulls and goats, and the ashes of a heifer sprinkling the unclean, sanctifieth to the purifying of the flesh :

"How much more shall the blood of Christ, who through the eternal Spirit offered himself without spot to God, purge your conscience from dead works and to serve the living God?" (Hebrews 9: 11-14)

Here he is cleverly re-introducing the idea of human blood sacrifice and he states that it is superior because it is the blood of a holy person. This is not the teaching of Jesus or Abraham. All Jesus ever spoke of were practical ways that people could change their thinking and their actions so that they would not build up a debt for the future through selfish or wicked ways. So the idea of remission

through blood sacrifice is not supported by Jesus. In any case Saul (Paul) seemed to be unaware that Jesus did not actually die on the cross. So his idea of sacrificial human blood was defunct from the start. It seems he was not fully able to give up the idea imbibed from childhood that guilt from sin can only be removed through shedding blood. He did not realise that Jesus had travelled from another country with a completely different message.

No intelligent person would seriously believe that killing a holy man was a method for the removal of their own debt of misdemeanours. To harm a holy person in that way is actually listed as one of the most grievous sins, incurring many terrible lifetimes of punishment as a result. So did Saul (Paul) inadvertently pre-select the intelligence level of the people who would follow his ideas? If this is so, it would explain how over so many centuries very few Christians have sought to trace the source of the innovative teaching of Jesus; where it is clear he did not agree with killing for any purpose. And it is also clear that the people who followed him did not understand his teaching (see below).

Thus it is not too difficult to demolish the concept that human beings have a short cut to redemption of their evil past, through merely believing the false idea of sacrificial blood. Also to believe that a person can lead a profligate life as long as they wished; then be immediately absolved of all that by a decision to take on a contrived idea of redemption, is one of the most unreligious concepts to come forth from human lips. Along with this Christian idea of exclusive access to redemption comes the judgement, that people who have lived an honest and good life all along, are not saved because they do not take on belief in the blood and the cross. How absurd is that? None of this is Jesus' teaching in any way.

WERE JESUS' FOLLOWERS DISCIPLES?

The word 'disciple' comes from the word 'discipline'; but it has become changed to mean a follower. Originally such a follower would accept the teaching of his teacher and the disciplines which were part of that teaching. So the first requirement of the follower, so as to be considered a disciple, is to listen and properly understand the teaching of his teacher. Reading the New Testament we have :-

Matt. 13:3 "Therefore speak I to them in parables : because they seeing see not; and hearing they hear not, neither do they understand."

Luke 18:34 "And they understood none of these things: and this saying was hid from them, neither knew they the things which were spoken."

Matt. 16:11 "How is it that you do not understand that I spake it not to you concerning bread, that ye should beware of the leaven of the Pharisees and of the Sadducees?"

All these statements relate to those who were the close followers of Jesus. These are clear references giving evidence that those who followed Jesus did not understand his teachings. If this was only on a few specific occasions then I am sure that the gospel writers would not have included them. It is more than likely that they did not include many other similar references so as to ameliorate the perception of those who had, by that time, become called "disciples".⁸

So the passage of time has attributed the term "disciple" to mean those who clearly did not understand the teaching being given to them. Also they have gained the status of "saint" by those who wished to elevate these followers to a higher status. If they did not properly listen and understand Jesus' teachings how could they have reached the status of saint? Jesus clearly warned them to leave a town or place where people were hostile, so as to avoid persecution.⁹ Yet they nearly all became subject to some form of violent death as a result of trying to teach people who rejected their teachings. Thus ignoring Jesus' advice does not give them a high status. Calling their deaths 'martyrdom' instead of disobedience and stupidity, also does not make the situation any better. It is merely a cover-up.

All those persons referred to as saints in India have many writings associated with their teachings. Either they have written these themselves or their followers have recorded them. These teachings are all about living a good and honest life and seeking the peace within which never fades; the core of what Jesus' taught. There is a book called, "The Cloud of Unknowing" written in the 13th century by an unknown English follower of Jesus. This man was clearly a great mystic and a saint. The teachings of St. Francis of Assisi are also holy teaching of the same high order. So all true Christian saints have wise writings associated with them.

Where are the teachings of those followers of Jesus who have been called "saints"? It was written that Jesus gave his followers the power to become sons of God.¹⁰ This is what it means, that if followers understood and lived his teaching they would, as holy men like Jesus, be able to teach others from their own experience. But he gave other conditions. He said that they must, "remove the beam from your own eye" first before attempting, "to remove the mote from your brothers eye."¹¹ Here he means do not attempt to teach others until you have purified your own inner self first; else it will be "the blind leading the blind".

So should we take the lack of teachings from those so called disciples as evidence that they did not put to practice the teachings of Jesus? If so they

⁸ See - McDonald, James (2011) : Beyond Belief : Garnet, Reading UK : ISBN 978-0-86372-345-2; Evidence of editing and other tampering by Christian authorities with Christian scriptures and history.

⁹ The Gospel of Matthew 10:14. "And whosoever shall not receive you, nor hear your words depart out of that house or city ..."

¹⁰Gospel of John 1:12 - "But as many as received him, to them he gave the power to become the sons of God."

¹¹ Gospel of Matthew 7:5 "thou hypocrite, first cast out the beam out of thine own eye: and then shalt thou see clearly to cast the mote out of thy brother's eye."

should not be referred to as either disciples or saints. Simply recording sections of Jesus' teachings in a gospel does not qualify for sainthood; journalist maybe; but not disciple or saint. If those reporters can be called "saints" having not understood Jesus teaching, nor lived their lives by it, then we can all become called saints in the passage of time. This only degrades the idea of the word "saint" and for those that are true saints, their status gets dragged down too.

FROM WHERE DID JESUS' TEACHING ORIGINATE?

Further to the above evidence that the followers of Jesus did not understand his teaching we have the following :-

Matt. 15:6 - "Are ye also yet without understanding?"

John 8:43 - "Why do ye not understand my speech? (is it) even because ye cannot hear my word."

These statements refer to the general public who were listening to his teachings. Here is clear evidence that the people of Palestine could not follow the language of Jesus, neither could they grasp his ideas. In both the above cases where lack of understanding has been demonstrated (disciple or public); we should not forget that all those people were present with Jesus and had the advantage to question him and get clarification of what he was trying to teach them. An advantage which no European has ever had. If the people of Palestine had been reasonably successful in further questioning, then we can be sure the gospel writers would not have included any reference to lack of understanding.

The above is more reason for Europeans to have realised that they had a greater difficulty in really understanding Jesus' teachings. If they had taken this clue given to them by the gospel writers, then they would have sought to discover the source of Jesus' teachings and where it was he went between the age of 13 and the time he returned to Palestine. This way they could have established a basis for a deeper understanding of what Jesus was saying. But with hindsight we now can see that the beginnings of Eurocentricism was an internal mental blockage, preventing them from seeing that they did not really understand. There is no greater ignorance than the type which convinces its victim that he already has true knowledge and hence no need for further instruction.

This blindness or mental blockage viz. "We know the truth from our gospels." is what drove the European Christian missionaries to ride roughshod over the established beliefs of many nations around the world. Had they truly understood Jesus' teachings they would have seen that all those nations were not really in need of their (false and incomplete) ideas about what Jesus taught.

After the Christian belief system had been established by the Emperor Constantine it became nearly impossible for a free thinker to seek out the source of Jesus' teachings, unless it was for himself only and he never would speak it to

another. Later, under Emperor Theodosius, the harsh penalties which were imposed for publicly departing from the prescribed Roman doctrine¹² would have prevented individual attempts to discover where Jesus was taught the wisdom which he had. Here is the essence of the Eurocentricism mentioned above. Building on the habit of telling others how to think and how to live their lives, on the basis that, "I know better than you"; a way of acting which the Vedantic culture and philosophy of India has never imposed on anyone.

Yet despite this lack of enquiry into the source of his teaching we can, in this century, find out the answer. There have been many historical accounts recently unearthed which mention connections of Jesus with India.¹³ We need not examine these at this stage. Instead we can use this information to begin a search by looking at teaching which would have existed in India when Jesus was alive.

There are many systems of belief in India. Many of these have existed for thousands of years prior to the birth of Jesus. There are currently many languages in India. Many of these have also existed for millennia. All traditional Indian languages have their origin in the Holy Sanskrit language; the language of the Vedas. If Jesus did travel to India it could only have been with some knowledge that there was valuable teaching there. This location he may have obtained from the Essenes who were a Jewish sect who had a history of contact with India and to which his family belonged.¹⁴

There were many belief systems extant in Palestine and the surrounding areas at the time Jesus was there in his youth. All of these sects had very different ideas about religion. Also we can guess there were many sects in India which had their own way of belief. If Jesus wished to find teaching which was of the best value he would not seek it in any of these short lived sects; either in the Palestine area or in India. The few examples which we can understand of Jesus' teaching shows that it is not short term. It is universal and can apply to all people at all times. It is as valid today as it was then. This points us towards a system of knowledge or righteousness which is ancient and can sustain its relevance over many thousands of years. Recent archaeological discoveries of the Indus valley has shown us that Vedanta is such a system so let us start our search there.

¹² See "In Search of the Loving God" by Mark Mason. ISBN 0 9658477 4 8 Dwapara Press Oregon USA. 1997.

¹³ See "The Unknown Life of Christ" by Nicolas Notovitch. "Jesus died in Kashmir" by Gordon & Cremonesi. "The Fifth Gospel" by Fida Hassnain & Dahan Levi. "Jesus in Heaven on Earth" by Khwaja Nazir Ahmed. "Jesus Lived in India" by H. Kersten. "The Crumbling of the Cross" by Faruqui. "Journey into Kashmir and Tibet" by Swami Abhedananda.

¹⁴ See "The Fifth Gospel" by Fida Hassnain & Dahan Levi. ISBN 978 1 57733 181 0. Dolphin 2008.

EXAMPLES OF JESUS' TEACHING FROM VEDANTA

New Testament Examples

Subject:- Worship or Prayer. Reference :- Matt. 6:5&6

(5) "And when thou prayest thou shalt not be as the hypocrites are; for they love to pray standing in the synagogues and in the corners of the streets, that they may be seen of men. Verily I say unto you they have their reward.

(6) "But thou, when thou prayest, enter into thy closet, and when thou hast shut thy door, pray to thy Father which is in secret; and thy Father which seeth in secret shall reward thee openly."

Today we can equate the word 'synagogue' to 'church'. So what is Jesus saying? Clearly the common practice at his time was for people to gather in one building and direct prayer (or worship) to their God the Father (the Creator). This, in the presence of each other to be seen and heard by each other. Also in the belief that their God would accept and hear their prayers to Him. We can guess that they were doing it this way either because their forefathers did it (i.e. habit) or that the religious leaders of the time told them that this was the way (i.e. compulsion). Maybe the Jews had the Eurocentric approach as well.

Jesus' teaching advises against this established practise; so much so that they could not really change it or even begin to give it up. This is clear because Saul of Tarsus set up a following of people who were directed by him to meet in churches and pray together. Either he was not aware of Jesus' teaching in this respect or he disobeyed it. In either case this teaching of Jesus has been of no effect in general, as all so called Christians still meet today in a building and pray together. Yet they have in the scriptures which they are supposed to follow, teaching which advises against it. If the Jewish practice was so strong that this teaching from Jesus was ignored from the very beginning, then from where could he have discovered that there was a more effective method of prayer?

In the ancient teaching of Vedanta we have the following :-

"Some wise people consider that inward worship is the means of liberation. Therefore wise people delight only in inward worship."

From the Mandala Brahmana (Upanishad) 78:11 6:10

"Inward worship or mental concentration is indeed the means of attaining to the holy state. Those who possess a mind endowed with the power of inward concentration see and realise what is good (the nature of the true Self). Through mental concentration (prayer or worship), great seers created objects by mere wish. All depends upon this power of the mind. Therefore they say that the power of inward concentration is the supreme means of liberation."

From the Maha Narayana Upanishad. 79:12

Liberation is a benefit or result of 'worship' in this context. Therefore worship as a verb (action) is equated to 'praying to'; seeking a result or benefit. Hence we can quite easily equate "inward worship" with "pray to thy Father in secret." Also taking "inward" to mean, "not open to other people to hear". Whatever Jesus' understood by the Sanskrit words for that phrase he has translated it in the above way for the people of his time and place. There is no equivalent method of worship (or prayer) in the Jewish scriptures at that time. If there were such teaching then his audience would have recognised it and followed it. Also he would have reminded them about it.

To add to the above Jesus would have read in the Bhagavad Gita various verses in connection with how to focus the mind on the Creator (prayer).

From Chapter 6.

10 :- A devotee should always try to concentrate his mind living alone in solitude, having subdued his mind and body and got rid of desires and possessions.

From Chapter 18.

52 :- Dwelling in solitude, eating but little, speech, body and mind subdued always engaged in meditation and concentration, ended with dispassion:

53 :- Having abandoned egoism, violence, arrogance, desire, enmity, property, free from the notion of "mine" and peaceful, he is fit for discovering God within himself.

Here the concept of being alone when practising devotions is well established in Vedanta. Jesus clearly learned this in India.

In Matthew chapter 6 above, Jesus' teaching on this subject there are two aspects; hypocrisy and effectiveness of prayer. As far as hypocrisy is concerned he used, "thou shalt not". Meaning that he was instructing his audience to give up the described habit of hypocrisy (includes egoism, violence, arrogance, desire etc. mentioned in verse 53 above). But as far as his concept of prayer was concerned he did not use "thou shalt". In accordance with the method of Vedanta he was passing on the best advice and leaving the decision up to the ones who wished to follow it. He was not telling them how to live their lives; but only giving advice on how to live. Yet it was necessary to say "thou shalt not" as a way of saying that in order to be in a position to have the option of choosing effective prayer, you must give up the hypocritical habit first. Vedanta works in the same way; there is a strong advice aspect to get you on the right track and out of your established bad habits; followed by the added options from which you are free to choose the one which suits you; when you are ready to do so.

Here is our first example of the source of Jesus' teaching coming from the ancient system of Vedanta, which is the same today as it was then.

This concept of an individual approach to worshipping and coming close to the Creator within oneself was completely alien to the Jews of the time. So much so that Saul of Tarsus (Paul) was unable to embrace it and he continued the old Jewish method of compelling everyone to pray together. Continued into the present in disregard of Jesus' advice.

Subject:- Anger. References:- Matt. 5:22; Luke 6:28&29

Matt. :- "But I say unto you, That whosoever is angry with his brother without a cause shall be in danger of the judgement: ---"

Luke :- "Bless them that curse you, and pray for them that despitefully use you.

"And unto him that smite thee on the one cheek offer also the other."

The Jews of Jesus' time were clearly living with the rule "an eye for an eye"; the established teaching of their forefathers. There was no tolerance of transgressors; they stoned them to death without a trial; barbaric in the extreme. If they had been tolerant and forgiving people, Jesus would not have needed to say those things quoted above. They were angry with Jesus and they planned to kill him. Where is the tradition of tolerance in that? They could not abate their anger. If there had been teaching in their own scriptures which taught such tolerance, they would have heard Jesus' teaching and would have tolerated him with his ideas. Jesus' knowledge of the Jewish scriptures was impeccable. There was no tradition to which Jesus could refer, to remind them about tolerance. If on any subject there was a tradition, he always quoted it to them. However, in India he had read the following (my comments in brackets):-

"One should bear patiently with abusive language and never insult another; nor should he in this embodied state, create enmity with anyone.

"One shall not return anger for anger; when abused he shall speak gently for the welfare (of all)."

Narada Parivrajaka Upanishad. 3:42-43

"If you have any anger against a wrong doer, how is it you do not have anger against anger, as it (the original anger) forcibly blocks (the path to) duty, wealth, love and liberation?

"My salutation to the anger against anger (i.e. control of anger), which well sets ablaze its substratum and which gives one dispassion and awakens one to one's faults." Yajnavalkya Upanishad. 28-30

This is where Jesus understood the spiritual value to the individual in abating anger and having tolerance towards the wrong doer. The selfish side of the ego is weakened by this method. He was teaching them this principle for their own good. But they would not listen. Even after the Jews thought they had

eliminated Jesus, they continued to seek out and destroy all his followers. Once again evidence that they could not follow his teaching and live by the principle of using tolerance and not anger. This same weakness is what caused the Roman Inquisition many centuries later; more evidence that Christians of all ages cannot hear the teachings of Jesus and tolerate "the wrong doer". Instead they are addicted to the Eurocentricism which grew from the seeds of the original Roman intolerance of the transgressor. How many thousands (or maybe millions) of free thinkers, labelled as heretics, were murdered by their own so called Christian leaders, has not been recorded. We know it went on for many centuries (some local records do show many thousands).

One of the most remarkable aspects of Vedanta is its tolerance of all aspects of individual beliefs. Atheists are accepted into the debates which they hold. This approach has found its way into Hinduism which derives most of its ways of understanding spiritual matters from the Vedanta teaching. Be sure that Vedanta is not confused with Hinduism in your mind. The word 'hindu' does not appear in any Vedanta text.¹⁵ Traditionally Hindus always saw clearly that all religious approaches come from the same Creator and have been tolerant of all. The last century saw radical changes to this approach due to the intolerance infection given to some Indians by the British, who were ignorant about the spiritual traditions of India; Ignorant Eurocentricism raising its ugly head. The British had a will to supplant Indian religions with Christianity.

People in India, Hindu or not, know the Bhagavad Gita and try to live by its tenets. Their tolerance of all people comes from such verses as :-

"Even if a man of the most sinful conduct worships Me with undeviating devotion he must be reckoned as righteous, for he has rightly resolved." Bhagavad Gita, chapter 9 verse 30.

This teaching Jesus knew from studying Vedanta.

The current divisions in India made between Muslims and Hindus came about due to British and European ignorance of the fact that all beliefs in a divine Creator are created by Him. More proof of the damage done by Eurocentricism. Read the letter by Lord Macaulay to his father (part quoted below), so as to understand the intentions of the British to annihilate Hinduism.

"We are introducing a new education system in India. If it is followed, within a century there will be no Indian who will be proud of his native land. ---- It is my firm belief that, if our plans of education are followed up, there will not be a single idolater (Hindu) in the respectable classes in Bengal, thirty years hence.

¹⁵ Quote from Swami Satyananda 2008 Vrindavan UP India. "Vedanta is not a religion, it is a way of life. That is the difference. This is the beauty of it. Anyone can come to Vedanta. Vivekananda used to say. 'Vedanta will make a Christian into a better Christian, a Muslim a better Muslim, a Hindu into a better Hindu.' That is very beautiful, and it is correct also." i.e. Vedanta is a universal teaching for all mankind.

And this will be effected without any attempt to proselytise. --- I heartily rejoice in the prospect."¹⁶

What more evidence do my readers need to prove that Eurocentricism has been such an appalling and damaging thing to other cultures around the world? Europeans need to wake up and accept other cultures and recognise the responsibility for the damage they have done; and are continuing to do across the whole world.

Previous to the British intervention in India people from all religious beliefs lived side by side with no conflict coming from their different ideas of the Creator or of worship; as they did in Palestine prior to the Eurocentric creation of a new Jewish state there. In India they met each other as equal Indians, the question of, "which religion are you?" was not in their minds in their day to day dealings. These facts are not recorded or known, only by few people today. It is the disease of religious intolerance from Europe which has infected modern Indian thinking. We need to realise that this ignorant and blinkered way of life called Eurocentricism is ruining the world. If anything needs to be eliminated it is not the culture or beliefs of other nations but Eurocentricism instead. People from the USA are now some of the greatest perpetrators of Eurocentricism (given to them by their ancestors); telling others how to live their lives; using military might if needed.

It should be clear from the above that Jesus brought this concept of tolerance and forgiveness of the transgressor from Vedanta, where it has been firmly established for many thousands of years. To be truly Christian (following Jesus' teachings) means to wholly accept all other's beliefs and established cultures.

Subject :- Steadfastness following a teaching. Reference :- Matt. 7: 24 to 27

(24) "Therefore whosoever heareth these saying of mine, and doeth them, I will liken him unto a wise man, which built his house on a rock. (the person who is endowed with steadfastness).

(25) "And the rain descended, and the floods came, and the winds blew, and beat upon that house; and it fell not: for it was founded upon a rock.

(26) "And every one that heareth these sayings of mine, and doeth them not, shall be likened to a foolish man, which built his house upon the sand. (the one who is not ready for spiritual study).

(27) "And the rain descended, and the floods came, and the winds blew, and beat upon that house; and it fell: and great was the fall of it."

Never before had there been teaching in Palestine which advised people to either study teaching and follow it for life, (the house on the rock) or **not** to hear

¹⁶ Taken from - Macaulay (1876) The Life and Letters of Lord Macaulay : New York : Harper & Brothers.

it at all if there would be no possibility of lifetime commitment (the house on the sand). The Jews of Jesus' time were obliged to follow the scriptures by their religious leaders; with no choice. This was irrespective of whether they were ready to follow them. No one knew of the damage to a person's life which could arise if they started to follow holy teaching, then later decided to stop. This is the real subject which Jesus is telling with the 'rock' and the 'sand' options of house building. We need to hear what he is saying not only what is written; and that there is no language of compulsion in these verses. He only gave the choices.

Vedanta is quite clear that each person has a different previous life and a different destiny. There will come a time when each person is ready to follow holy teaching; then is the best time to start. If they begin before that there is the chance of a life of spiritual failure. The worldly part of their life is not affected; it is only to do with the spiritual progress. If children at school are told that they must pass advanced level examinations before the elementary ones have been passed, then they will more than likely fail. In Vedanta we have :-

From the Satyayaniya Upanishad verses 29-31 :-

"If having embraced asceticism (living by holy scripture), one does not remain observing its laws, he is known as 'fallen from grace' such is the injunction of the Vedas (begin study when ready).

"To that great fool there is no liberation seen even in tens of millions of years." (meaning rebirth as an animal for a long time).

This is the subject which Jesus was drawing attention towards. The two key words of 'fall' and 'fool' are common in the above examples from the New Testament and Vedanta.

In the Bhagavad Gita there is a similar verse Chapter 3 verse 32 :-

"But those who carp at My teaching and act not thereon, deluded in all knowledge and devoid of discrimination, know them to be ruined." The advice of Shri Krishna (the Lord God incarnate).

This is the same warning to those who would start to study holy scripture and then turn against it. The person who ignores religious subjects is in a better position spiritually. A person who "carps" is the same as one who "doeth them not"; because in order to be in that position they must have begun to study the subject. The people of Jesus' time, and the Christians ever since that time, have not seen the spiritual significance of a person being made to follow holy teaching before they were ready to do so. If they were to have realised the spiritual damage that can be done, the Christians would not go around the world forcing their religious ideas into every one's life, regardless of their previous progress or previous faith system.

This is the damage done by making the 500 year Christian doctrine of reincarnation into a heresy in the 5th century. The idea that we have one physical

life only, rules out the concept that we have many chances of future opportunities to make progress in spiritual matters. Previous to the 5th century all Christians followed Jesus' teaching on reincarnation. Now few European Christians have any knowledge of it due to the ignorance of their previous leaders who abolished the doctrine. If a parent who smokes has no knowledge that smoking tobacco leads to ill health, then their children will grow up as smokers and will find it difficult to believe any bad stories about smoking. Anyone who doubts that references to reincarnation were removed from the gospels should read the research done in this current decade by James McDonald.¹⁷

"The evidence that early Christians tampered with their holy texts is overwhelming. We have every sort of evidence that it took place. For many centuries the mainstream churches denied that there was any evidence of tampering in God's divine word, but this position is no longer tenable, and no mainstream Church now seeks to deny that biblical texts were tampered with."

The importance of beginning spiritual study at the right time in life was what Jesus discovered during his study of Vedanta in India. He brought this knowledge to Palestine, but the people did not understand him and could therefore not follow his teaching on this subject. Hence many centuries of Christian proselytising (Eurocentricism) have done damage to the perfectly adequate belief systems of other cultures. Also European Christians have shot themselves in the foot by eliminating the knowledge of reincarnation from their belief system. Thus limiting their own understanding and their own chances.

Subject :- The Creator is Within All. References :- Luke & John

"The Kingdom of God is within you." Luke 17:21

"Even the Spirit of truth; whom the world cannot receive, because it seeth him not, neither knoweth him: but ye know him; for he dwelleth with you, and shall be (realised as being) in you."

John 14:17

To the Jews, as with the Christians of all ages, their idea of the Creator is a being who is remote from the individual. Indeed, any access to Him has to be through their idea of an intermediary; a priest or bishop. But these statements of Jesus do not corroborate the concept of a remote creator. The verses above on prayer in a secret place are clear that intermediaries are not necessary. Both "within you" and "in you" indicate a personal closeness to the Creator. We all know this as little children under two years. ("and become as little children.")¹⁸

¹⁷ McDonald, James (2011) : Beyond Belief : Garnet, Reading UK : ISBN 978-0-86372-345-2; Good research into the centuries of editing and other tampering with Christian scriptures and history by Christian authorities.

¹⁸ See Matthew Chpt. 18 verse 3.

It is necessary to introduce here the eastern concept of ellipsis. This way of making profound statements is not well known by Europeans. It is a system whereby the listener's intellect is engaged in the dialogue by omitting words from the context or hiding the meaning. The missing text has to be provided by the listener's own knowledge of the subject or through a process of contemplation of the words heard. This may also mean decoding an analogy.

An example of this method is when Jesus said to his disciples, "Take heed and beware of the leaven of the Pharisees and of the Sadducees." Matthew 16:6. Leaven is the hidden substance put into dough. The disciples clearly did not understand that he was not speaking of bread. Eventually, with his help, they worked it out that he was talking about the hidden guile of the Pharisees, contained within their doctrine.

The statement, "The kingdom of God is within you", needs to be worked on in this way. Clearly a kingdom without a king is not a kingdom. So Jesus is telling them that the king is also within. This is the meaning of Jesus' statement; but it requires the listener to make some input of his own to connect with the real meaning. Also the term, "Spirit of truth" can be equated to the same king as above; because Jesus says, "He dwelleth with you", meaning the Creator. The hidden meaning and missing words can be easily deduced from the context.

But there is no concept in the teaching of the Jews that the Creator dwells within the soul of each individual. So the Jews, as with the Roman Christians, were having nothing to do with this concept. They did not understand what he was telling them and have based a belief system on their own ideas; not those of Jesus. So where did Jesus gain this realisation of the Creator dwelling within each human soul?

In the Bhagavad Gita chapter 10 verse 12 we have :-

"I am the Self seated in the hearts of all beings."

This is the essence of the Vedanta teaching; that the Creator dwells in all of His creation. He is experienceable by all creatures. When an individual human being realises that s/he is not the physical body only, then the realisation that the soul is identical with the Creator dawns. This is called liberation or salvation.

There are so many references to this inner unity in Vedanta. Here are a few of them.

"Like the butter hidden in milk, the Pure Consciousness resides in every being. That ought to be constantly churned out by the churning rod of the mind." Amritabindu Upanishad, verse 20.

"The one Supreme Personality of Godhead is hidden within everything. He is all-pervading. He is in everyone's heart. He witnesses everyone's activities. He lives in everyone's heart. He is the witness. He is consciousness. His is transcendence. He is beyond the modes of nature." Gopala Tapaniya Upanishad, verse 115

"That highest Bliss exists in one's own Self. It is calm, identical with liberation, indescribable, and unborn. Since It is one with the unborn knowable (Creator), the knowers speak of It as the Omniscient." From the Mandukya Upanishad Karika, verse III-47.

"God, who is one only, is hidden in all beings. He is all-pervading, and is the inner Self of all creatures. He presides over all actions, and all beings reside in Him. He is the witness, and He is the Pure Consciousness free from the laws of Mother Nature."
Varaha Upanishad.VI-11:

Hence it is clear that Jesus read these scriptures and himself became liberated from the ignorance that man is limited by his physical body. Hence he taught that God is within each person so as to lead their thoughts in that direction. His teaching was new and his approach was also new. The Jews could not deal with it; since it did not resonate with their traditional teaching. Few since that time have been prepared to either discover where it came from or to accept that some people of Jesus' time knew where to go to find deeper wisdom, i.e. India.

Subject :- Inner Purity. Reference:- Matt. 5: 8

"Blessed are the pure in heart for they shall see God."

Here it is necessary to introduce one of the key Sanskrit words used in Vedanta. It is "**antahkarana**" which is what Jesus meant by the word "heart" in the above verse. But we have no equivalent term for this Sanskrit word in any European language. Why not? you may ask. Contrary to the idea that Europeans have knowledge of all things, there are many concepts in Vedanta which do not exist in the minds and lives of most Europeans. These concepts have arisen from the true knowledge of the human soul; how it became embodied and what happens to it after the body stops breathing. This knowledge is not like much of the European idea of knowledge; based on theories which themselves are based on other theories. The knowledge in Vedanta is based on experience. Where the subject is about the human soul then the experience is that of a highly spiritually enlightened soul. It is because such experience is not within the European materialistic type of life, that we have a lack of concepts and hence a lack of words relating to those concepts.

The Vedanta understanding of those inner intangible parts of the human psyche is deeper and more fully researched than that of Europeans. Due to the phenomenon which I have called Eurocentricism, it is difficult for people of the European stock to accept that people of eastern cultures may know more about the human being and the soul. Hence Eurocentricism is a block to their progress in that subject.

The Vedanta understanding of the five parts of the human being is summed up in a statement from the Bhagavad Gita, chapter 3, verse 42 :-

"The senses are said to be superior to the body; the mind is superior to the senses; the intellect is superior to the mind; and what is superior to the intellect is the soul."

Here - body, senses, mind, intellect and soul are put into their respective places relevant to each other. Only the body is physical; the others are subtle and cannot be measured by the sophisticated instruments of the Europeans. But the philosophy of Vedanta takes this analysis further. The mind and intellect are said to be further sub-divided with four different functions; all of which we can relate to or can experience at times. That part which deals with day to day thoughts is called **manas**. Another part which has the power to tell us that a thought or desire is beneficial or not is called **buddhi**. The part which assists reflection, reasoning and memory is called **chitta**. The fourth part which carries a sense that we are an individual is called **ahankara**, it is where we hold all the tendencies to desire things for our life; some of these we have carried over from a previous life. Some desires are useful others are detrimental (see my paper on Creativity and Self -discovery for a useful diagram of the human being).

It is these four parts, **manas**, **buddhi**, **chitta** and **ahankara** which combine to form what is called the **antahkarana**. Which literally means the inner organ and is the meaning of "heart" in the verses on pages 20/21. All these are concepts which we do not have equivalent words for in European languages. So the translation of the words of Jesus cannot be entirely accurate. Vedanta encourages us to purify the **antahkarana**. This means eliminating unhelpful desires and thoughts from the various parts of the **antahkarana**; i.e. being pure in heart.

"When the mind, with its attachment for sense-objects annihilated, is fully controlled within the heart and thus realises its own essence, then that Supreme State (is gained)." Amrita Bindu Up. 4.

"The aspirant who strives with assiduity, purified from bad karma and perfected through many births reaches then the Supreme Goal." Bhagavad Gita chapter 6, verse 45

"Within (the heart in) the body, where the vital force has entered in five forms (five pranas), is this subtle Self to be realized through that intelligence by which is pervaded the entire mind as well as the motor and sensory organs of all creatures. And It is to be known in the mind, which having become purified, this Self reveals Itself distinctly." Mundaka Upanishad III-i-9:

All this Jesus summed up in that simple statement from Matthew chapter 5. This is the way to understand it; and to know that he discovered the importance of this purification when he studied Vedanta. There is no equivalent teaching to be found in the scriptures of Palestine extant at the time of Jesus.

Examples From Other Sources of Teaching

Above we have some examples of Jesus' teaching taken from the traditional gospels. Examples which were clearly new to Palestine. This teaching clearly did not come from that part of the world. There are many other examples within Vedanta of teaching identical to that of Jesus. Also there is evidence here of where Jesus obtained the knowledge and ways to put it over to his audiences.

Now let us look to another scripture which contains Jesus' teaching. The Gospel of Thomas is widely accepted by scholars and all open minded Christians. Discovered in the 20th century it had remained unedited and with no parts missing for nearly two thousand years. It clearly contains identical teaching found in the four traditionally used gospels. Hence no doubt they are Jesus' words. It also shows how there had been editing of those traditional gospels; and there are examples of teaching which are not found in the four main gospels, (i.e. they may have been edited out for purposes of doctrinal contrivance).

Subject :- One in a thousand. Reference:- Thomas 23

Jesus said, "I shall choose you, one out of a thousand and two out of ten thousand and they shall stand as a single one."

The Jewish approach to religion had no concept that only some of the human race needed to deal with belief in a Creator. This could be due to the mistaken idea which Jews once held, that they are the chosen people of God. A true understanding of the Creator is that all people are equal in His view; and all religious ways have emanated from Him.

The earlier subject relating to steadfastness, if properly understood, shows that some are ready to study spiritual subjects and others are not. This is a similar way of looking at there being only a few who can benefit from approaching belief in a Creator. We accept that not all children will become ready to take advanced level school examinations or go on to university. Why can we not apply this simple logic to the subject of spiritual study? This is the effect of religious Eurocentricism; forcing everyone to accept their belief ideas and making belief in reincarnation into a heresy. Thus depriving all future generations of the knowledge that they can take up or progress and fulfil the belief in religious subjects when they are born next time as a human being. There is no compulsion to start now.

Also we have an incident in the gospel of Matthew chapter 22 where a man came to the wedding feast without the proper wedding garment. Here Jesus is pointing us to have the correct attitude to study and worship (wedding means seeking union with the Creator). Hence in verse 14 he says :-

"Many are called but few are chosen."

This is the same subject about those that are ready to study holy scripture. To "be called" is to get the chance of a human embodiment.

The ancient system of India was simple. Those who could deal with the spiritual purification of their life should do so and become human examples of honesty, non-violence and compassion towards others. These and other good qualities are the natural outcome of a person who is awakened to the reality that the spirit of the Creator lives in all creatures; including one's fellow citizens. This arises when a person studies and lives by the concepts which are embodied in the Vedanta philosophy.

There is nothing better than a few good examples of people living less by animal instincts and more by noble principles. Their presence in society will inspire others to follow the good example. This way all those others in society who are unable to study or follow the spiritual subject, will not be deprived of some progress in their human embodiment. They do not all need to be religious or spiritual. Shri Krishna said in the Bhagavad Gita, chapter 3, verse 21.

"Whatever a great man does is followed by others; people go by the example he sets up."

Also the 20th century, little known Divine man Shri Guru Deva said :-

"By combining the knowledge of the scriptures with the wisdom of the Creator, happiness and peace will be gained. In addition the resulting good conduct of the devotees will bring happiness and peace to even the unreligious.

"Through the resulting increase of love for one another in society, the community can be established in peace, orderliness and good conduct of the individuals. The nature of a society built on righteousness is that all members of the community wish others to profit from its advantages. These will then bring peace and happiness even to those who are not religious."¹⁹

Here there is no statement about non-religious people being bad or wrong. They are accepted as part of any society. They will also benefit from the example of the good way of life of those who have chosen to live by righteousness. His Divinity Shri Guru Deva was a master of Vedanta philosophy, who understood this principle very clearly. He was the spiritual leader of Jyotirmath Ashram.

¹⁹ From the book "The Life and Teachings of His Divinity Shri Guru Deva" ISBN 978-0-9571665-3-0

The above is very clear to me in England where I live. Since I was a child vast numbers of people and their children have deserted the Christian church. The attendance numbers are the lowest for many centuries. A recent UK national survey in 2018 shows that only 2% of people in the 18 to 24 age range, identify themselves with Christianity; in the 45 to 54 age range it is 11%; a dramatic fall off. Yet there have always been large numbers of English people who are good, honest and loving. This is true of those who do not call themselves practising Christians. The example of noble people is enough to inspire others to emulate them.

I spent many years as a professional person working in the City of London UK (the square mile). I can say with certainty that the speed and efficiency with which insurance, banking, accountancy, legal and many other matters are dealt with, is due to the honesty and integrity of the people who work there. The efficiency of doing deals in any of these things arises from the belief and confidence in a mere handshake. The one who does not work in this way in the City will not find a welcome there. This high level of human integrity known in the City of London is recognised world-wide as its special characteristic. Others in the world are influenced by this. This honesty and trust is not to do with religion. A little yeast in the large mass of dough will raise the whole mass. This is the principle here; and it has been shown to work. It is not these non-religious good people who have spoiled religion in our society.

It has been recently shown with more and more prosecutions and prison sentences for bishops and priests, that it is the so called religious people whose hypocritical and despicable actions, that have despoiled the idea of religion.²⁰ Jesus' teaching was to give up worldly wealth and seek the love of God instead. He made it very clear that those who gathered unnecessary wealth could not find that thing which he called, "the kingdom of heaven".

All religious leaders in England live in luxury and have great wealth. The Anglican church has an investment portfolio which is in tens of billions of pounds sterling (GBP) and rising. They are one of the largest land and property owners in the UK. Yet there are vast numbers of people in the UK going hungry and are homeless. This sounds very much like the story of Lazarus and the rich man in the New Testament.²¹ I wonder how many of those rich and arrogant so called Christian leaders realise that they will go to a horrible hell at the death of their current body? They are not presenting the good example that they teach others to follow. Jesus called this "hypocrisy".

²⁰ Many religious leaders and priests have abused their position of control and have become financially corrupted or have sexually abused children and others under their control. Some of these are now in prison.

²¹ New Testament : Gospel of Luke Chpt. 16 verses 19 to 31

Hence from the example of the few good people influencing others, we can see a little deeper into the statement which Jesus made where he says “two out of ten thousand”. He was bringing to the people of Palestine the ancient concept that belief in a Creator was not needed for all people. This was certainly new to them. The Jewish idea was a ‘one size fits all’. Everyone was compelled to become religious. The hypocritical aspect of it was that those who preached their religious concepts to the people did not live by them in their own lives. Similar to the “despicable actions” of the so called UK Christians mentioned above. Jesus actually pointed this out to his audiences.²²

It is very clear that when all people are compelled to become religious that it does not work in reality. To implement such a regime requires a large organisation employing so called religious people; such as the large spiritually useless organisation we now have in the UK called the Christian church; which has clearly gone fully off track and does not live by Jesus' teaching. It is no wonder that intelligent people who can see the reality, no longer wish to be considered members of the Christian church. Hence we can begin to see the practical value in Jesus' statement “two out of ten thousand” etc. If this was such a revolutionary idea, where did he get it from?

In the Bhagavad Gita, one of the principal writings of Vedanta, we have :-

“Among thousands of men scarcely one strives for perfection, and of those who strive and succeed, scarcely one knows Me in truth.”
Chapter 7, verse 3.

Such statements are often made without explanation. The person studying such text is advised and trained to look deeper and seek the inner meaning. This is the method of Vedanta. The follower has to become fully engaged in discovering the practical value of the scripture as applied in ordinary life. Also it is part of the teaching that it is not meant for all people. In the Maha Upanishad verses 105 and 106 we have the following (my comments in brackets) :-

“One who teaches the unity of God in all people to an ignoramus or half-awakened (person) will (in effect) plunge him into an endless series of hells. (i.e. spiritual failure will result in animal rebirth).

“But a disciple whose intellect has been well-awakened, whose craving for objective enjoyments has been extinguished, and who is free from all ‘expectations’ is rid of all impurities born of nescience; the wise teacher may instruct him.” (nescience = ignorance)

Here the advice is clear that religious or spiritual teaching given to a person who is not yet ready to hear it may only be detrimental. Jesus knew this; the Jews did not. They were unable to understand the principle or to apply it. It is

²² New Testament : Gospel of Luke Chpt. 11 verses 37 to 54 and Matthew Chpt 23 verses 1 to 29

the concept behind the parable of, "remove the beam from your own eye first"²³. Hence it is clear that Saul of Tarsus was also not able to grasp the concept that a few well trained and purified people would really benefit human society by their example. Instead he followed the old Jewish idea of compulsion for all people in religious matters; and a one-size-fits-all formula which clearly does not work. All it did was to create a basis for dissension and conflict leading to murders and wars in the many centuries of Eurocentric Christianity.

Later the Roman Emperor Constantine followed Saul's idea and compelled everyone to follow the religious way which became called Christianity (see Appendix Three) This is what I am now calling the seeds of Eurocentricism. Make a quick review in your mind of how much conflict, murder and hatred this idea of Constantine created in subsequent centuries; not only in Europe but worldwide. Instead, the teaching of Jesus stated above, if understood and followed, would have created stable and noble communities throughout Europe; producing a more valuable Eurocentricism (if that were possible). The world would also be in a better situation now.

In the manuscripts discovered in Tibet describing the life of Jesus, it is reported that he answered a question in the following way :-

Priest :- "How can any nation properly survive if it did not recognise the authority of its religious leaders?"

Jesus :- "Even without priests and religious elders, people are governed by the infallible law of Mother Nature, which teaches the people that they have to account for their words and actions. True knowledge of human life outlives people; religious leaders are fallible, the truth in holy teaching is not. True knowledge leads naturally to true love. Such love is the great saviour of mankind. Through this way of understanding in life, the people were always able to retain the truthfulness and sincerity of their souls."

The concept of the one in a thousand spoken of by Jesus and taken from the Bhagavad Gita shown above is clearly behind the parable of the two houses also detailed above; the one built on rock and the other built on sand. If we use the Vedanta method of study we can look to find the deeper meaning in this parable and soon see that Jesus means, "Don't think to become a seeker of God until you are sure that you are ready to commit your life to it. Otherwise trying to be religious and failing in it will only lead you to a great spiritual fall."

And I will add to that advice – don't disregard the knowledge that your soul will return here in another body, as it already has in the current one, unless you are perfectly sure beyond doubt that there is no such thing as reincarnation. Not

²³ New Testament : Gospel of Matthew Chpt. 7 verse 5

accepting the doctrine of reincarnation which Jesus taught, will lead you to making mistakes in this life which may give you a difficult life next time.

Modern Christians are like their original Jewish and Roman mentors are completely unable to accept the above simple concept of "two out of ten thousand". Instead they go around preaching their own misguided interpretation of Christian doctrine to everyone; in high streets, on radio and television and at the doorstep; completely oblivious of the potential damage they can do. This is very prevalent in the USA; ex-Europeans (includes ancestors) suffering from the Eurocentricism which they carried across the Atlantic ocean to America.

Their arrogance extends to coming back here to the UK and trying to push their false ideas onto UK communities. Both Mormons and Jehovah's witness people have come to my front door peddling their Eurocentricism, not knowing where it started before they began to suffer from it.

According to what we have seen above, these proselytisers would be far less hypocritical if they went home and worked hard on improving and perfecting their own lives. This way they could become a real good example and truly inspire many others without preaching to them. This is the real message behind Jesus statement of "two in ten thousand".

Subject :- Renouncing the world. Reference Thomas 110

Jesus said, "Whoever has found the world and become rich, let him deny the world."

Contained within this glib statement is one of the keys to success in the spiritual work of the soul. We need to fully unpack it if we are to understand what Jesus wanted us to embrace. To help with this unpacking we can look in the New Testament for clues. In Luke chapter 6 verse 24 we have :-

"Woe unto you who are rich! for ye have received your consolation."

In both of these we can see that Jesus is advising against having too many or unnecessary worldly possessions. By the word 'rich' in Luke he does not mean only money, but worldly possessions of land and property etc. In Thomas 110, 'rich' may mean 'rich in spiritual knowledge'. Also by the phrase 'woe unto you' it means from the spiritual side of life your chances are less. Clearly there is no detriment to the worldly side of life from being rich. Hence the consolation means that because we are temporarily content (consoled) with our worldly possessions, this in some way is a cause of 'woe' to us, which we need to dig out of the saying. The phrase 'deny the world' could be part of the answer.

In Matthew chapter 19 the same subject came up when a man who had great possessions (verse 22) came and asked, "What good thing can I do?" (verse 16). Jesus answer was simple (verse 21), "Go and sell that thou hast; and give to the poor -- and come and follow me." Surely we understand that he means to give

up everything. After selling everything he would only have money. This should be given to the poor; after which the man would have nothing.

Clearly this incident was recorded to illustrate how the people of Jesus' time were obsessed with worldly possessions, much as most people are today. This arises because there is a belief that possessions will bring happiness to the person who has them. There are young children in India today, when asked about not having many of the modern gadgets and toys; they have answered, "My life is happy without these things." So there is another view of what makes us happy.

The only concept they had in Jesus' days with regards to renunciation was a form of monasticism practiced by the Jewish sect called the Essenes. But for the ordinary person they did not have a scripture which advised them to give up worldly possessions, or they would have found Jesus' remark reminded them of it and it would have been an easier concept to embrace.

So once again Jesus is bringing a new concept into the lives of the ordinary people of Palestine. An idea which they did not have from their own scriptures. And again we can show below that this idea of renouncing or giving up the sense of ownership of possessions came clearly from Vedanta. It is this practice of letting go of the attraction to the world and to people which is so spiritually liberating. In Vedanta it does not always mean physical deprivation, but more connected with a mental state of being free. We can say that really our possessions possess us not the other way around. Meaning that the space in the mind is cluttered with them giving us less scope for contemplation on our relationship with the Creator of all things.

In the Bhagavad Gita, which Jesus would have most certainly read, we have in chapter 4, verse 21:-

"Hoping for naught, his mind and self controlled, having abandoned all possessions, performing action by the body alone, he incurs no bad karma."

And in chapter 13, verse 9 we have :-

"Unattachment, non-identification of self with son, wife, home, and the like, and constant equanimity in the occurrence of the desirable and the undesirable ;"

This is closer to Jesus' sense of denying the world. It can mean, 'denying to the worldly life' -- its chance to cause attachment and to bring us expectations in the form of desires and the like.

In the New Testament (Luke chapter 14 verse 26) Jesus said what seems on the face of it an uncharacteristic statement :-

"If any man come to me and hate not his father, and mother, and wife and children, and brethren and sisters, yea, and his own life also, he cannot be my disciple."

I say 'uncharacteristic' since Jesus always spoke of loving all others and especially in Matthew chapter 19 verse 19 where he asks us to;

"Honour thy father and thy mother and love thy neighbour as thyself."

The clue here is the use of the word 'his' at the beginning and end of the verse in Luke 14. All in the list are included in 'his'; meaning the possessive case. The idea that mother and father etc. belong to us is the error here. Becoming unattached to them is very difficult, but no spiritual discipline is easy, otherwise all could achieve it without help from great teachers like Shri Krishna and Jesus. This is why Shri Krishna advised us to become detached and not identified with all worldly things around us - "self, son, wife, home and the like" mean the same as "father, mother wife etc. and his own life (self)". Hence this makes more sense of "let him deny the world" in Thomas 110.

Deeper reflection on all the above shows us that Jesus' teaching is entirely compatible with the teaching of Vedanta if we interpret it in the way which is spiritually beneficial to us. All Jesus wanted was to present the options available so that we could progress in our contemplation of communion with the Father. He never said that any of these possessions were sinful or bad. In Thomas 110 Jesus said "let him"; not "he shall" or "he must"; the choice is ours. In the Bhagavad Gita, after giving much teaching to His disciple, Shri Krishna says in chapter 18 verse 63 :-

"Thus has wisdom more profound than all profundities been declared to you by Me. Reflect upon it fully and act as you choose."

There is no compulsion - the choice is ours; to live by it or not.

In a Tibetan scripture kept in a Buddhist monastery it gives an example of Jesus' teaching about all our possessions; here Jesus is speaking with the authority of the Creator Himself, hence the first person pronoun :-

"Jesus said :- It is to Me and to Me only, that you owe all you possess, all that is around you, whether above or below."²⁴

This is the real truth behind "deny the world". All worldly matters whether they are our possessions or our worldly thoughts and plans, we believe either belong to us or are originated by us. Jesus is telling us in the above statement that all comes to us from the Creator himself. We have nothing of our own in reality. Hence we can fully unpack the statement from Thomas 110 as :-

"Whoever has discovered the reality of the nature of the worldly life, he will become rich in true knowledge. Let him therefore deny the idea that he possesses anything in the worldly life and thereby find liberation."

²⁴ From "The Unknown Life of Christ" by Nicolas Notovitch, taken from Tibetan sources of Jesus' teachings.

Here again we have proof that Jesus knew the basic principles of Vedanta, and he spoke them in his own inimitable way to the people of his time.

CONCLUSIONS

The language used by Jesus in the above quote from the Tibetan record is not fully understood by most of those who purport to follow Jesus in one way or another. By 'language' I mean the use of the first person singular pronoun 'Me'. Hence the situation with those who are supposed to be followers of Jesus can be summed up in the following verse spoken by a man who was, in principle, the same as Jesus; the Lord Shri Krishna. He says in the Gita chapter 9 verse 11 :-

"Fools disregard Me as one clad in human form, not knowing My higher nature as the Great Lord of beings."

Only such men can truly use 'Me' or 'My' and similar terms and speak such knowledge. But few people realise what this statement means. Let me help a little. We are all born again and again in different beings or creatures. In each birth we carry the same sense of Self; yet we become fully identified with the particular body which we find ourselves in. This causes us to have no knowledge or memory of previous births. Hence it was easy for previous Christian leaders to abolish this aspect of Jesus' teaching and to get away with it. Those who have remembered themselves and that they are not the body only, have no problem with the concept of reincarnation. For the others they have doubts; hence they cannot know that the Lord of all beings (the Creator Himself) can choose to embody a portion of Himself on this planet for the purpose of re-establishing righteousness when it has been disregarded by the human race. Hence Shri Krishna also said in the Gita, chapter 4, verses 7 & 8 :-

"Whenever there is decay of righteousness and rise of its opposite, then I embody Myself, O Bharata.

"For the protection of the good, for the destruction of the wicked and for the establishment of righteousness I am born age after age."

The Great Lord of beings (the Creator) has the choice to come and go as he pleases. We as individual souls do not have that choice. We are bound by the laws of Mother Nature. If we act unrighteously we may not get a human body next time. Jesus came to this planet to formulate the ancient knowledge of this process and teach it to all who would listen. He knew where to go to find teachers of that knowledge since within himself he is the knower of all things.

There are many people, mainly so called Christians, who do not wish to embrace the possibility that Jesus could have gone to India to receive teaching.

We can view their fixed ideas in much the same way as the crop circles incident in the UK in the 1970s. Two young men in the southern area of England decided to create a hoax. They devised a method to create patterns of circles in fields of ripe wheat or barley. This they did in the dead of night in such a way

that the circles could not have been made by humans. The reaction of the public was astonishing. Many theories arose about these mysterious circles; some saying that they were created by visitors from outer space. This went on for nearly 15 years. The public media were also very involved; making many investigations. The culprits were not discovered. Eventually when they decided to confess their hoax they were not believed. After showing publicly how they did it, the public declared the two men "fake tricksters". Saying that they were trying to create a claim to fame.

After only 15 years people had become accustomed to the fake ideas of the circles and were not prepared to accept the truth when it was put before them. So we can easily understand why modern Christians are not happy to give up the fake aspects of the story of Jesus and his teachings after seventeen or eighteen centuries. They are now mentally addicted to the established false ideas

These modern Christians need to answer the simple questions, "Where did Jesus gain the knowledge which enabled him to speak the way it is recorded that he did?" If it was the Palestine or surrounding area then, "Why did the people he taught both not accept him nor understand him?" Also if it was that area then, "How is it that no other people of his time had the same knowledge base?"

Such objections to Jesus leaving the land of his birth to gain the best teaching he could get, are not based on knowledge of both Jesus the man and the culture in which he spent his first decade or so. Instead such people base their objections on a projection from within their own psychology, which is formed from information put there by generations of misguided understandings of Jesus. With these understandings Jesus is not known to be the "Great Lord of beings."

We need to have a starting point of at least an understanding of what a divine man is. This means any attempt, however little, to remove those old misguided ideas and begin with a clean slate in the mind. There are so very few people born into this world who have a magical description of their birth situation associated with their coming into this world; as is described in the New Testament surrounding Jesus. We cannot expect to base our understanding of such a person, which has our own experience of human life as its way of understanding. Hence we need to study and research the nature of divine personages and form a basis of understanding within our own minds, so that we can begin to understand how Jesus would have viewed the world around him as he grew up during his childhood years. These years are key to anyone forming the basis of where their life will take them; and what their mission will be.

I have made it clear in this paper that the focus of the peoples of the Palestine area during Jesus time would not be towards barbaric uncivilised Europe; but towards such places as India and China where established high cultures had been known to exist. The established and perfected system of teaching Vedanta had existed for millennia prior to Jesus' birth. It is inconceivable that the

educated and spiritually minded people of Jesus' time would not have known about this. It is historically recorded that the families of both Jesus and John were associated with the Essenes of the Jerusalem area. These people were the keepers of traditional and orthodox ways of implementing the Jewish faith. They also had historic connections with India. This information about the Essenes and the cultures of Palestine and the Far East is available to all who seek it.

Jesus was a clean, wise and just person from his birth. Such was the kind of birth situation which was given to him by the Creator of this world. So the way he would have viewed the hypocrisy, ignorance and barbarism of the people around him would have driven him to find a way to both understand those people's motives and to find a way to cure them of their ignorance of the purpose of human life. If he did not form that mission for his life then, in those early years, then wherever he went after the age of twelve, he would never have come back to Palestine. But the New Testament is clear; he did come back as a very wise person and with the mission to help cure the people of the land of his birth of their intolerant and barbaric ways of living. So he taught love and humility.

This paper is really about where Jesus went and what he studied during those years in between his youth and his return to Palestine. Also I have taken evidence from the New Testament which has sought to understand the inaccuracies there and to build on the truthful side of it. The blanket view that the New Testament is the "Word of God" is one of the most unhelpful views that a person can hold. This view was planted in the minds of Europeans by people who we can now say are responsible for the formation, birth and nurturing of Eurocentricism. We all need to realise the truth that Jesus studied Vedanta.

There is in all honesty no such thing as "The Word of God". But there are plenty of words of wise and enlightened people who have been inspired by close proximity of their own soul to the being of God the Creator. Compared to the vast quantities of spurious and short lived words which the human race has produced, such wise words have been seen to survive the thick and thin of human civilisations, where most of those other words have sunk away into obscurity. Hence if we ascribe the title "Word of God" to those more enduring passages of human wisdom, this is a more reasonable and acceptable way of describing the good parts of the New Testament. This way accepts that it will have errors and inaccuracies contained within it, especially when we consider the fact that rarely do those wise, divine people write their own words, but that lesser, fallible people are the ones we rely on for the record.

There is no doubt that the so called Christian church has been off the rails for many centuries; the evidence above shows that they do not follow Jesus. Instead we have an organisation which has been shown in the past, and more especially in the present, to have abused its position of control over peoples lives (the ugly spectre of Eurocentricism). More and more we are seeing that both the Catholic

priests and bishops; and those of the Anglican church; are guilty of child sexual abuse and other forms of corruption and mismanagement. They are not Christian. Their moral position is really now zero in this 21st century. Yet in the UK they are plugged firmly into the establishment of the country's politics, and it seems they are unstoppable. This position of theirs, as with that of the Pope in Rome, is now obsolete and not performing any function which Jesus would recognise. These Christians are so blind and arrogant they cannot ever see it.

But another thing is also certain. The huge weighty express train of the Christian church has gained so much wealth and momentum over the centuries, that it cannot be stopped in its tracks. But it is surely going along a downward sloping track. It will not stop even though it has run out of fuel (moral status). The driver has long deserted the express train (direction and control) yet it still continues on its way. The best thing all communities can do where there is a dysfunctional Christian control within, is to make sure the points (laws) along the track are changed, so the train will travel to a dead end; then all on board will disappear into obscurity and never be seen again.

What we need to learn is that whenever any habit becomes hardened in the course of time then it is very difficult to remove it. This applies to alcohol and drug addicts as much as it does to large organisations.²⁵ When a habit contains concealed falsehood, as it is now shown to be true in respect of the Christian belief system, then the habit of believing and behaving in spiritually unbeneficial ways is extremely difficult to remove. This is especially the case when the habit of Eurocentricism has become so normal over many centuries. This all began with the Roman creation of the Christian faith idea. Gradually it has become so accepted that it has worked its way into the very heart of UK society and similarly around the world in other countries.

The world needs to free itself of this obsolete Eurocentric faith system. And in its place teach the real knowledge contained in Jesus' teachings; based on the eternal righteousness which is to be found by all who seek it, in Vedanta. No other formula will put this world on the right track and save it from destruction.

And don't forget

"Vedanta is not a religion, it is a way of life. That is the difference. This is the beauty of it. Anyone can come to Vedanta. Vivekananda used to say. 'Vedanta will make a Christian into a better Christian, a Muslim a better Muslim, a Hindu into a better Hindu.' That is very beautiful, and it is correct also." i.e. Vedanta is a universal teaching for all mankind, which is independent of all religion.

Quote from Swami Satyananda 2008 Vrindavan UP India.

²⁵ See Appendix One on addictions.

APPENDIX ONE

To help a little with the last point about addiction I quote here from the book "The Biography of Jesus - His Life and Teachings"²⁶. In that book the Journey of Jesus with his cousin John to India is fully described. In part three of the book there is help with understanding how the world is in such a sorry state. It discusses the subject of addiction very well; quoted below.

The Addictions of the World

In many ways the path towards union with *Bhagavān* (the Creator) is one of addiction. Yet this trait within the human being can lead towards freedom from suffering or to an increase in suffering. Addiction is the cause of most of the worlds difficulties and the suffering of many hundreds of millions of people in the modern world. Yet it can also be said that it is the cause of great joy and happiness for many. The message of Jesus in his teaching is to tame this trait of addiction; so that the option of freedom (salvation) can be exercised and the option of suffering can be eliminated. So let us briefly examine the subject of addiction and firstly see, if we can, how the addiction of the world causes suffering.

Let us look at the word 'addiction'. In English it is defined with such other words as :- habit, compulsion, obsession, craving or infatuation. Yet the noun 'addict' is defined as :- devotee, fanatic or enthusiast. Here in these two uses of the term we can see the potential for either suffering or for earnestly seeking the path of salvation.

The Sanskrit equivalent word for addiction is *prasakta*. This is defined with such terms as :- attached, cleaving or adhering to, fixed or intent upon, devoted to, clinging to the world, being in love or enamoured. Here again we can see there is the potential for either suffering or liberation from suffering, depending on how the individual applies the human trait which this concept of addiction entails.

This is the key point here; the use by the individual of addiction. The laws of the world fall heavily on some forms of addiction, because it is considered that such forms are the cause of suffering of more people than the addict alone. Hence we have laws which apply penalties to the substance addict (drug user) and those who supply them. We have laws which penalise the person who habitually steals from others, either shop-lifters or bank robbers

²⁶ Private publication - information available from saraswati.soc@btinternet.com

etc. The list of such illegal addictions is large. In many cases the person who is either fined or imprisoned will soon go back to their addiction and re-offend. This shows that the trait within the person has not been addressed or remedied by the penalty; and it shows that it may be a mental or deeper difficulty which the addict has.

There is no such thing as genetic pre-determination or other ways of explaining or excusing this trait in the addict (see Appendix Two) It can easily be shown that people with the same habits and the same genes, that some do and some do not become addicts. For example the drinking of alcohol is a common habit with many millions of people. Yet they do not all become alcoholics; so it is not alcohol *per se* or the habit of drinking it which causes alcoholism. It is not the physical world which is at fault here; it is in the mind of the individual. It is the pre-disposition in the mind of the person which leads them to excess and on to addiction. This pre-disposition cannot be proved to be genetic. But it can easily be shown to be related to the mentality of the person and may well relate to the circumstances of childhood, while in their mother's womb or, more likely, may be from a previous life. The Alcoholics Anonymous movement in the UK is a sure example of the mental approach. Their cure is seen to be through applying a new mental attitude, no medicine or physical method is used. Their success is in changing the mental addiction first.

In this current age many hundreds of millions of people are suffering due to addiction. But here I do not limit the term to alcohol, stealing or drugs etc. The number with these illegal addictions are tiny compared to the overall suffering of humanity in this modern age, of huge wealth. There are relatively few people who cause far greater suffering than these illegal things, yet such people are not considered to be acting illegally. Who are they?

Lust for more and more power in one way or another is addiction. Greed for more and more money, wealth or land is addiction. Many politicians and people with large businesses are guilty of these addictions. Stop! and ask the question - "Why, when a person has accrued 5 million dollars (or pounds) is he obsessed with getting another 5 million? When will he stop seeking more wealth? The same can be asked of power in either business, politics, belief systems or land ownership. Their obsessions have caused the population of the world to fall into relative poverty, landlessness, ill health and suffering. Yet instead of putting these

addicted people into prison, the world has been coerced into applauding them for their addictions, from which suffering is caused to those other than the addict. There is a finite quantity of such things as food, wealth and land; hence taking more of these than needed deprives others. All these things, wealth, power, land, food etc. are provided by Mother Nature for everyone to benefit from equally.

We all have one human life to live here on this planet. It does not need proving that we cannot take with us any of the gains which we accrue in the worldly sense, when we leave here. Most of the people who amass huge wealth cannot explain to themselves how they expect to use it all in this one life or indeed why they wanted so much wealth in the first place. Addiction is the only way of seeing and understanding this. Those who achieve great power in politics or in businesses, also cannot explain to themselves how such a power can give them lasting happiness; they are also addicted.

Politics and business rise and fall, come and go like the leaves on trees; all intelligent people can see that fact clearly. But can we all see how desire for excessive power, excessive wealth and excessive land ownership are the result of an addiction? If such excesses are used for the good of all then there is more acceptability of taking excess. But can we see how selfish excesses are the cause of much suffering to people other than the addict? If we could see that fact clearly we would put many politicians and business people either into prison or hospital, until their selfish addiction is cured. Such is the true injustice of this world. Some selfish addictions are punished, but far more damaging addictions, as mentioned above, are applauded and permitted. Religious leaders cannot claim exemption from these addictions in this age. As such they are not acting in the way that Jesus recommended that they should act. It is because of their addictions that many religious leaders are as far away from Jesus' teaching than anyone could get. The same applies to politicians and wealthy people. The damaging effect of these addictions cannot be removed all the while we elect people to rule us who have secret desires to have these excesses for themselves. It is untruthful and corrupt for leaders to hold to such desires. In the words of Shri Svami Satyananda :-

"The world created by God is not bad, it does not lead to bondage. But the world created on the basis of "**I and mine**" that is the cause of all bondage. That is to be illuminated and eradicated. And that

would be eliminated by knowing the true nature of Man; what he is."

How do we find the knowledge of the true nature of Man?

"Truly the declarations of Sages whose minds are uncoloured (purified) constitute (holy) scripture. And, they who are pure at heart and in whose vision there is no division (duality) are regarded as Sages. The immature (ordinary) person can hope to see the light of Truth only with the aid of a scripture and the knowledge of the nature of an enlightened person."

Yoga Vasishtha III : 95 ancient Vedic scripture.

It is only by applying the eternal laws of Jesus, and other Divine Incarnations, to our human life here during our brief stay, that the world can be saved from the suffering caused by selfish addictions. This means we should all become addicts of his teaching and not addicts of worldliness, wealth, power, land or property ownership. The least effect of this new addiction will be that the individual who takes it on themselves, will cease to suffer and may well find eternal happiness. The greater effect will be that life for many hundreds of millions of people will have less suffering, when their leaders are honest and true to Jesus' teaching.

This can only be effective if we as individuals make effort to purify our own lives. The Chinese saying that , "A large pot can be filled with many drops." is relevant here. People follow the example of goodness.

This is what Jesus came here to tell us. But do we have ears to hear it?

Taken from the book "The Biography of Jesus" by Allan Bailey-Hawkes.

APPENDIX TWO

ADDICTION

The Progress of the Soul's Prison Over Many Lives

This short essay describes the gradual process of attraction and desire progressing to a state of addiction, as understood in the Vedantic way of seeing human life. It can take many life-times for this to happen. Sanskrit words are used with a description of their meaning. In many cases there is no direct equivalent word in European languages; because European culture does not base itself on the knowledge of rebirth of the human soul and the *karma* which is carried from one life to another.

(*karma* - means the accumulated effect of words, actions and thoughts throughout life.)

The first stage towards addiction is called *rāga* - meaning attraction to an object or thing or event etc. i.e. the desire for things.

(*rāga* - means vehement desire for, affection, desire, passion.)

This leads in time to *lobha* which is a more intensive desire when the desires have been established for many lives. Here with *lobha* we want an unlimited supply of the desired object.

(*lobha* - means avarice, strong desire, greed, eager desire for, covetousness.)

Then this will activate *bhāva- āsrava* which is the soul losing its resistance for the desire or the desired object. This is uncontrolled desire. The individual is overcome.

(*āsrava* - impel soul towards objects or to generate *karma*, affliction, defilement, impurity)

This situation then activates the influx of *karmic* particles (possession of attitude or *samskaras*) to infect or enclose the soul and to cause an addiction. This is called *dravya-āsrava*. The soul is not truly infected but is enclosed with the effects.

(*samskara* -means embedded effect of past *karma* carried to the next incarnation.)

Then the soul becomes bound to the desired object. It is an irretrievable situation.

This then leads to several harmful habits which affect the person's life.

<i>mithyātva</i> -	perversity of outlook.
<i>avirati</i> -	absence of self control.
<i>pramāda</i> -	negligence of duties.
<i>kaśāya</i> -	passion - the influence of <i>karmic</i> particles.

This means that all actions or *karma* of mind, body and speech are affected.

Anyone can get into such a state of addiction, but they cannot get out of it without help from outside. Like falling into a deep well. Those who understand the severity of this situation will seek the help of a Self-realised or spiritually accomplished person and the traditional scriptures. This is the only way their soul can be saved from this situation.

Note :- to have a longing or strong attachment is not necessarily bad-*karma*; i.e. actions, words or thoughts which harm others. Hence may not create *karma* as described above.

APPENDIX THREE

With kind permission of the author I have reproduced the entire text of Appendix Three from the book "The Biography of Jesus - His Life and Teachings"

This text speaks for itself and is the evidence from Saul himself.

SAUL OF TARSUS

In modern times people have suffered exposure due to unguarded words being put in some way onto the internet or through what is known as social media. Their suffering arises because private words spoken or written to one person or a group of people have found their way across the world. It may not have been the intention for their words to be known by such a wide audience; hence their inner secret intentions or character have become exposed.

Contrary to modern belief, the above is not a new event. The same thing happened to Saul of Tarsus (later called Paul) who wrote private letters of advice to individuals or groups who were having some difficulty in following his directions. He had no intention that those private words would one day be spread across the world. However, this is what has happened. Hence, a forensic examination of them reveals Saul's motives and plan along, with some inconsistencies in his accounts and in his teachings. Read on!

The significance of this Appendix centres around the information in other parts of the book, which states or infers that the modern religion called Christianity has very little to do with Isha's (Jesus') teaching. There is plenty of evidence from Saul's own words that this is the case. Anyone can check this evidence for themselves by simply reading the letters (epistles) written or dictated by Saul of Tarsus under the name Paul. The evidence is put together here in such a way that the above statements about the religion can be easily verified. This shows that Saul modelled his new sect or cult on Judaism. The fact that some of those letters may not have been Saul's makes no difference, since they are also doubtful spiritual advice and have formed part of the basis upon which Emperor Constantine formulated the state religion, later called Christianity.

What we have to realise, by being simply honest to the facts, is that the sect started up by Saul of Tarsus was originally called the Christian Jews. At that time the word 'Christian' was an adjective to describe the nature of the Jewish sect which he started. Later the noun part of their title was dropped, leaving the adjective to take it's part. People who live by that upgraded adjective, believe they are following Isha (Jesus). But the truth is, the pillars upon which their belief is founded were all invented by Saul; they are not the teachings of Isha, but are rooted in Judaism. The crucifixion, the blood of the cross, the resurrection and the ascension; all these are events, not teaching. And as this book, along

with plentiful historic record shows, all those things did not happen in the way that followers of the adjective believe.

In this Appendix I will not refer to Saul of Tarsus as a saint. This is with due respect for this word as expressed in the Introduction to Part One.

There are two basic ways to write an account of past events, based on written or spoken evidence of others. The first embraces the principle of honesty and truth; this would be without any personal agenda but to seek only to let all the evidence from others provide proof of what happened. The second may not embrace truthfulness to the same high degree and is with a personal agenda or with pre-conceived notions; this would then seek for evidence in those accounts of others, which would give support to the notions which were part of the agenda. Other contrary evidence might be ignored.

For this book I have made a sincere attempt to embrace the first of these ways. However, it is my firm conviction, from his own words,²⁷ that Saul of Tarsus was more inclined to adopt the second way to support his own ideas.

Saul the Erudite Scholar

Saul was clearly a very skilful and knowledgeable theologian. He knew the Jewish scriptures very well and those of other established religions.²⁸ He later gave good Jewish religious advice in his letters (epistles). He was engaged to persecute the followers of Isha, who at the time were nothing more than an upstart Jewish sect, put down by the anger and rejection of the Jewish High Priest. These facts can be verified by anyone who reads the New Testament. It was this action of persecution that focussed Saul's mind on what this new sect stood for. Add the ideas in his teaching into the known history that Saul wanted to start his own Jewish sect, and it will become clear what it was he did later.

It is clear that he promoted his own sect under the name of Jesus Christ. In his Epistles he often says, "my gospel" or "my teaching". He does not refer to the teaching of Jesus (Isha), but only uses the power of the name of Jesus to underpin his own ideas and intentions. Knowledge of the power behind the name Jesus Christ came to him on that road to Damascus, when he knew without doubt that Isha was a man of God with miraculous powers.

The Meeting Outside Damascus

There is little doubt that Saul met Isha on the road to Damascus. This event is important evidence of two things. That Isha was living and travelling in a direction away from Damascus; and that Saul of Tarsus was a deceitful and crafty person. Hence it becomes a key issue to establish this event on the road to Damascus as evidence to both the part of Isha's life after Galilee and that the

²⁷ Romans 3:7 "For if the truth of God hath more abounded through my lie unto his glory; why yet am I also judged as a sinner?" Saul's justification for telling lies after he was caught out.

²⁸ We must remember that there was at that time no belief system called Christianity.

belief system set up by Saul was his own concept based on the name of Isha and the events of Isha's life. Predicted by Isha himself :-

"Many will say to me in that day, 'Lord, Lord, have we not prophesied in thy name? and in thy name done many wonderful works?'

"And then I will profess unto them, 'I never knew you; depart from me, ye that work iniquity.' " Matt. 7: 22 & 23

The language of these verses shows that Isha knew these things would happen in his own lifetime. The evidence in the New Testament gospels makes it clear to anyone that Isha was living after the attempt to execute him. He met his disciples several times and ate food with them. Ghosts or spirits do not eat food. Hence it was clearly Isha's physical body which the disciples met and dined with. This is the best indication we have that he survived the attempt to execute him. Death by crucifixion takes three days not six hours.

There is no evidence that Isha subsequently died in the Palestine area as there is no report of this nor knowledge of his tomb anywhere there. So where did his physical body go to? The idea that it evaporated by ascending into the clouds in the sky, is only for the less intelligent people, who have a belief that heaven is a physical place and that a physical body can go there and disappear. This idea was not reported by those who were present when Isha left them, it was added to the scriptures later.²⁹ Heaven is clearly a spiritual state or inner experience according to all belief systems. It is where the soul of man finds eternal peace and union with the Creator. Such a place cannot be known through the physical senses.³⁰ It was Saul who, in the early verses of the Acts of the Apostles and later in his epistles, turned the parting events reported by Isha's disciples into a mystical idea of physical ascension of Isha's body into the clouds. One who is firmly attached to the physical world, as Saul clearly was, can only think in physical ways. This idea pre-selects the type of people who will follow a belief system based on it.

So it can easily be established that Isha was alive and needed to leave the area as he was at risk of being re-captured by the Jews or the Romans. Saul reported that he was made blind. But he says that God did this to him with a bright light. Such an action by the Creator has never been reported in the whole of human history. The Creator does not do this kind of thing. If there is belief that He did it, then this belief needs to be extended to Him restoring that sight again later. The fact that a man, called Ananias, with mystical powers, was the one who restored Saul's sight, makes it clear that it was another man with mystical powers who originally took that sight away. (See John 9:39). Any action, which it may be assumed the Creator does, would not be able to be undone by a mortal human being; otherwise the concept of an omnipotent, all powerful Creator has no

²⁹ See the plentiful evidence of tampering with the gospels in "Beyond Belief" by James McDonald.

³⁰ See the model of the human being from page 84 onwards

substance. Hence it is clear that Saul was a deceiver. Also we should understand that after his sight was taken away by Isha, he then knew that Isha was a man who had the power of the Creator (or part of it). It was for that reason that Saul used the name "Jesus Christ" very often in his epistles, so as to carry the power of Jesus into his attempts to build a Jewish sect of his own; not truly from respect for what Isha was or what he stood for.

Saul's New Sect Established

So having established by evidence and reason in the above way that Isha was living and moving away from Damascus and that Saul was a deceiver, we could now look at some of the characteristics of Saul and his deceit. These were all part of the attempt to establish his own Jewish sect using the name of Isha (Jesus Christ) as the driving force to establish that sect. During this examination of Saul's deceit we should hold in mind that it was Saul's idea of a belief system which was the central theme of the cult or religion (called Christianity) set up by the emperor Constantine. This was done in the 4th century after Isha's birth and transformed a group of minority Jewish-Christian sects into a state sponsored religion; which was even at that time, a false concept of the man Isha and his teachings. This was later, in its edited and altered form, forcibly spread to the whole of Europe and to many parts of the world. Also we must not forget that European Christians have used the sixteen centuries which followed to further falsify that belief system;³¹ instead of making serious attempts to get at the true source of it; and to undo the damage done by Saul. Much of the evidence which would completely support this view is hidden away in the Vatican library. From time to time various documents have escaped from this prison, such as the Gospel of Peace of Jesus Christ.

Let us also be as kind to Saul as the circumstances permit. The first person he deceived was himself, but unknowingly. He is not the only person to do this. Many in history have done it based on false beliefs imbibed during child-hood, passed to them by grandparents and parents. Meaning that the mechanics of the way the Jewish belief system works were ingrained in Saul from childhood through strict orthodox beliefs. These mechanics included the concepts of Satan and sin; and about how blood sacrifice can atone a person's sense of guilt; so as to give some mental relief from their past misdemeanours. They really did believe that killing a goat or sheep gave them absolution.

The use of large purpose-built buildings (synagogues) was not what Isha taught but was clearly part of the Jewish belief system. Therefore we should understand that Saul was honestly convinced of those things which he taught, however far from Isha's teaching they may have been. But we must be clear that Saul's epistles were written long before the four Gospels of the New Testament were written down. Hence he had little chance to be fully acquainted with the

³¹ Evidence of falsification is abundant in "Beyond Belief" by James McDonald.

real message in Isha's teachings. Also we should realise that the Epistles were private letters to people who were having difficulty in following Saul's teachings. It is not likely that he ever intended them to be published globally; since they contain evidence of his crafty scheme to create a sect of his own. They were collected after he was executed and shared by his various groups. This has enabled us to get an insider view of what he was up to. It is possible that the Emperor Constantine also saw this side of Saul.

Saul could only know of those few things which Isha's disciples may have understood, which he then interpreted in his own way to suit his already established belief framework. This comes out clearly if the Epistles are read in the right way. But remember the New Testament makes it clear that those disciples did not understand what Isha was teaching them.

Saul of Tarsus was clearly a man who had the gift of speech which could make people feel either good or bad about themselves simply through ideas put into words. He was also capable of speaking about the aims of religion and associated methods in a convincing and erudite manner. Not only that, he was also a very well read and accomplished theologian. He knew well the old Jewish scriptures and was able to deploy their language in his own way to get people to do anything he wanted them to do. In short, he used the language of scripture to manipulate people; very much like cult leaders do in modern times. Clearly his aims were basically noble, however misguided they may have been. Much of the language of his Epistles is simply ideas, which have little practical value, reinforced with the word "gospel" and the phrase "Jesus Christ". These ideas were meant for the purpose of giving large numbers of people reasons to join and follow the sect which he designed, many of whom he had little or no real contact with. There is no doubt he had the main purpose of rejuvenating the Jewish faith system and of setting people back onto his idea of the straight and narrow path of religious obedience.

Saul's Attempt to Connect Jesus' Life with Jewish Tradition

This book is clear; Isha was most certainly of Jewish descent. However, his knowledge and hence his teaching are not Jewish. If these things were Jewish, why did his public disciples have so much trouble understanding what Isha was saying to them? Also why did the Jewish High Priest not accept his teaching? There is plenty of evidence in this book that the source of Isha's teaching was from India. This is why the Palestinians did not understand it.

Saul of Tarsus was not aware of this fact, for the simple reason that he knew very little of Isha's teachings. He says almost nothing about it in his Epistles. Saul's motive was simple - to create a new Jewish sect along revolutionary lines; but to avoid being dammed by the orthodox Jews who would have possibly stoned him to death, he pins the responsibility for it on Jesus Christ and calls those who followed his own sect Christian Jews.

Furthermore he seeks to establish that his new sect is traditionally Jewish in many ways but with a modern outlook. This was to try and recruit as many Jews as possible. The Jewish tribes and families were spread abroad during Saul's time. There were communities of them in Anatolia (Turkey), Greece, Italy and many other Mediterranean lands. If he could get them onboard with his new faith it would boost numbers and possibly appeal to the Greeks, Romans and Gentiles as well. This way he could achieve his idea of immortality by going down in history as the great teacher of his own new world Jewish belief system, but based on his own ideas of Isha (Jesus Christ).

"Now when they had passed through Amphibolis and Apollonia, they came to Thessalonica, where was a synagogue of the Jews.

"And Paul, as his manner was, went in unto them, and three Sabbath days reasoned with them out of the (Jewish) scriptures." Acts 17:1 & 2

"And the brethren immediately sent away Paul and Silas by night unto Berea : who coming thither went into the synagogue of the Jews.

"These were more noble than those in Thessalonica, in that they received the word with all readiness of mind, and searched the (Jewish) scriptures daily, whether those things (which Paul was telling them) were so." Acts 17: 10 & 11.

This shows that it was the Jews at first he wanted to convert over to his way of thinking. Later when the Jews in Jerusalem arrested Paul for the things he was preaching in the synagogues he asserted that he was a Jew.

"Paul said, I am a man which am a Jew of Tarsus, a city in Cilicia, a citizen of no mean city : and, I beseech thee, suffer me to speak unto the people (the Jews)" Acts 22 : 39

He does not state that he is a follower of Jesus Christ, but of the Jewish faith. Giving him authority to preach his new ideas about Jesus to the Jews.

Saul also makes it clear that he wishes to reform the faith of the Jewish people because he believed they strayed from the true path :-

"Brethren, my heart's desire and prayer to God for Israel is, that they might be saved (from their own iniquity)." i.e. the Jewish people.

"For I bear them record that they have a zeal for God, but not according to knowledge." (i.e. his own ideas.) Rom. 10: 1 & 2.

He tries over and over to link the advent of Isha (Jesus Christ) with the Old Testament characters.

"Now to Abraham and his seed were the promises made. He saith not, And to seeds, as of many; but as of one, And to thy seed, which is Christ. (confirming belief in a normal biological birth of Jesus)

"And this I say, that the covenant, that was confirmed before of God in Christ, the law, which was four hundred and thirty years after, cannot disannul, that it should make the promise of none effect.

"For if the inheritance be of the law, it is no more of promise : but God gave it to Abraham by promise." Gal. 3 : 16-18.

There are many more examples to show conclusively that Saul's idea was to create a new concept of the Jewish faith using the name of Jesus Christ.

Poor Memory or Proof of Lies

Deceivers are often caught out by inconsistencies in their reports of specific events. Saul's first description of the road to Damascus scene says that it was Ananias who instructed him some days later, to change his life :-

"And one Ananias, a devout man according to the (Jewish) law, having a good report of all the Jews which dwelt there,

"Came unto me, and stood and said to me, Brother Saul receive thy sight. And the same hour I looked upon him.

"And he said, The God of our (Jewish) fathers hath chosen thee, that thou shouldst know his will, and see that Just One and shouldst hear the voice of his mouth.

"For thou shalt be his witness unto all men of what thou hast seen and heard." Acts 22:12-15

The language of this report (and the following one) makes it clear that either Saul wrote the Acts or dictated them to a scribe. Also it confirms that the whole exercise is Jewish. Later in the second report, given perhaps after the first one, he says that it was Jesus Christ who instructed him there and then on that road to Damascus :-

"And I said, Who art thou Lord? And he said, I am Jesus whom thou persecutest.

"But rise and stand upon thy feet; for I have appeared unto thee for this purpose, to make thee a minister and a witness both of these things which thou hast seen, and of those things in the which I will appear unto thee." Acts 26:16 & 17.

These differing reports from the mouth of Saul himself indicate that he made up the instructions about what he should do after he had been made blind. It appears that he saw the opportunity to use the incident on the road to Damascus combined with the power in the name of Jesus Christ to start the process of launching his own Jewish religious sect.

Proof of Saul's Own Ideas of a Sect

Notice here where he underpins his own gospel by attaching the name of Jesus Christ. This same thing is still done by so called Christian groups :-

"In the day when God shall judge the secrets of men by Jesus Christ according to *my gospel*." Rom. 2:16 -

He does the same in the same Epistle again using the name of Jesus.

"Now to him that is of power to stablish you according to *my gospel*, and the preaching of Jesus Christ, according to the revelation of mystery, which was kept secret since the world began." Rom. 16:25

How does he know what knowledge was available in other parts of the world and many thousands of years previously? When did he hear the preaching of Jesus? He used Jesus' name only as support for his ideas; notice he says 'my gospel' not the gospel of Jesus.

He confirms that he is not following the teaching of Jesus in another verse, which also affirms he has made up his own gospel :-

"Yea, so I have strived to preach the gospel (his own), not where Christ was named, lest I should build upon another man's foundation." Rom. 15:20

Here Isha is just "another man" not a great holy man with the power of the Creator in his teaching and his actions.

Saul Confirms Isha is Still Alive

It is clear that Saul met Isha on that road to Damascus and did not know where or when he would reappear, because he confirms this in his epistles many times :-

"Waiting for the coming of our Lord Jesus Christ." 1 Cor. 1:7.

"For what is our hope, or joy, or crown of rejoicing? Are not even ye in the presence of our Lord Jesus Christ at his coming? 1 Thes. 2:19

"And then shall that Wicked be revealed, whom the Lord shall consume with the spirit of his mouth, and shall destroy with the brightness of his coming." 2 Thes. 2:8

"Until the appearing of our Lord Jesus Christ." 1 Tim. 6:14

"And the Lord Jesus Christ who shall judge the quick and the dead at his appearing." 2 Tim. 4:1

"Looking for that blessed hope, and the glorious appearing of the great God and our saviour Jesus Christ." Titus 2:13

He never uses the phrase "second coming" a phrase much used by later Christians. So it is clear that he knew Isha was still living and he guessed that he might turn up anywhere to teach people again. Saul did not know where Isha had finally gone to. So he had to mentioned often that he may come back into the scene again at some time. He seemed to welcome this possibility. From this it is also clear that Saul really believed he was promoting what Isha stood for, as there is an underlying sense that he believed Isha would have approved of all that he was teaching. This is why I say that the first person he deceived was himself. Hence it follows, all that he taught others was based on the original self-deceit of his own psychology.

Saul Creates His own Version of Blood Sacrifice

Saul details the ancient Jewish belief that shedding blood was the way (in theory) to gain remission of misdemeanours, or what they called sin :-

"For when Moses had spoken every precept to all the people (the Jews) according to the law, he took the blood of calves and of goats, with water, and scarlet wool and hyssop, and sprinkled both the book and all the people,"

"Saying, 'This is the blood of the testament which God hath enjoined unto you.'

"Moreover he sprinkled with blood both the tabernacle and all the vessels of the ministry.

"And almost all things are by the law (of Judaism) purged with blood; and without shedding of blood is no remission (of sins). Heb. 9: 19-22

Note: the shedding of blood here implies the death (sacrifice) of the goat.

Here he has reasserted the Jewish law with regard to remission of sin. Saul had previously spelt out that this ritual has to be gone through every year by the High Priest :-

"Now when these things were thus ordained, the priest went always into the first tabernacle accomplishing the service of God.

"But into the second went the high priest alone once every year, not without blood, which he offered for himself and for the errors of the people." Heb. 9: 6 - 7.

Saul's idea was to do away with the yearly ritual with the blood of an animal and introduce a once for all sacrifice carrying the same ancient principle of cleaning up past iniquities through blood sacrifice. If the old Jewish ritual had been effective there would have been no need to change it. But the change is not such a great difference in principle. So he is not departing too far from the Jewish tradition. Hence he uses the supposed death of Isha (Jesus Christ) on the cross as a means to introduce his new idea. He uses very clever wording, none of which comes from Isha or his teachings.

"But Christ being come an high priest of good things to come, by a greater and more perfect tabernacle, not made with hands, that is to say, not of this building.

"Neither by the blood of goats and calves, but by his own blood he entered in once (for all time) into the holy place, having obtained eternal redemption for us (a longer lasting redemption.)

"For if the blood of bulls and goats, and the ashes of a heifer sprinkling the unclean, sanctifieth to the purifying of the flesh :

"How much more shall the blood of Christ, who through the eternal Spirit offered himself without spot to God, purge your conscience from dead works and to serve the living God?" Heb. 9: 11-14.

No blood of Isha was taken from the crucifixion scene. None of his blood was sprinkled on the people there while he was alive. After he was taken down there is no report of his blood being taken from his body. So there was no shedding of Isha's blood in the manner required by ancient ritual.

This concept that the guilt of people's previous bad actions can be mitigated by shedding the blood of an animal has never been proved to be efficacious. Saul does not question its validity in this way; instead he accepts it as valid because he was brought up as a Jew to believe that it works, or is supposed to. It comes from ancient Pagan ideas of sacrifice.

Thus Saul introduces a new concept which goes against all the belief systems of humanity. A concept which states that people need make no effort to purify themselves, but have already been purified by the blood of a man they have never met, simply by their belief in an idea. Thus he achieves (on paper only) his object; which was to start a new version of Judaism using blood sacrifice, but avoiding the need to do this every year. He eventually sold this attractive idea to many gullible people. It is a Jewish concept not one of Isha; who only recommended good actions and good words as a means.

But notice he uses the phrase "*to come*" in verse 11 above. This implies that the redemption will come in the future. This is to get round the likely possibility that those who take on this new belief might not notice much difference in their practical life, but only in their inner sense of relief through belief. So they will not necessarily get evidence that it has worked for them, only an inner belief that it will work when they die. This crafty method avoids any after-sales complaints from those who take it on as a belief idea.

"For Christ is not entered into the holy places made with hands, which are the figures of the true; but into heaven itself, now to appear in the presence of God for us.

"Nor yet that he should offer himself often, as the high priest entereth into the holy place every year with blood of others.

"For then must he (Jesus) often have suffered since the foundation of the world; but now once in the end of the world hath he appeared to put away sin by the sacrifice of himself. (not Isha's idea in any way).

"And as it is appointed unto men once to die, but after this the judgment: (i.e. redemption will come at death of your body.)

"So Christ was once offered to bear the sins of many; and unto them that look for him shall he appear the second time (at the end of their life) without sin unto redemption. Heb. 9: 24 - 28

This whole idea of Saul is flawed, as it is clear that Isha did not die, hence his blood was not shed in the manner of Heb. 9:22.

Also to get around the anomaly of the sequence of events, Saul has to introduce the idea of Isha's resurrection; this allows both the blood and the cross ideas and the possible future appearance of Isha to co-exist.

No one who buys this idea can come back after death to make a complaint, when they have found that it does not work, and have found that instead they will have to be born again and go through a life which may be worse than the one they had before. It is clear that Isha did not teach this but that the wording in the gospels, compiled after Saul's letters, was adjusted to reflect some of these ideas of Saul; by that time adopted by the Christian Jews.

The Last Supper Scene

Saul appeared to know about the last supper where Isha broke bread and poured wine for his disciples (see 1 Cor. 11:24). Yet the reports of Isha's words in relation to the wine representing blood are inconsistent. In Matthew 26: v. 28 it says :- "*For this is my blood of the new testament which is shed for many for the remission of sins.*" Yet in Mark 14: v. 24 it says :- "*And he said unto them, This is my blood which is shed for many.*" No mention of remission of sins. In Luke 22: v. 20 it simply says :- "*Likewise also the cup after supper, saying, This cup is the new testament in my blood which is shed for you.*" Meaning only his disciples. No mention of others or for remission of sins. Two accounts do not mention remission of sins. Isha has indicated elsewhere that blood means devotion and flesh means teaching. Shed also means distributed. This can give a whole new meaning the those words of Isha at the supper.

Here it is clear that a Jewish scribe, when copying the documents of Matthew, seeing the word "blood" could not disassociate it from the annual ritual for remission of sins and has, in good faith, added the words about shedding of blood and remission of sins, to complete what he imagined the full meaning was. If Saul had read or heard such words then there is no doubt that he would connect the crucifixion with remission of sins. Isha did not agree with shedding blood. Also we should remember that Saul's ideas were already known at the time when the Gospels were finally written down in full and it is more than likely that the established teachings of Saul had influenced the final wording chosen from the various versions of the gospels rather than the other way around. This was to bring in a degree of consistency in the scriptures. Hence the words about shedding of blood could be an addition to the scripts by a scribe or could be one of Isha's allegories.

What is more likely is that Isha was saying to his disciples that they should not mourn his own departure if he were to die. But instead to remember him with joy and the celebration of a meal with wine. This he would indicate because death of the body can mean release of the soul and that for a purified person the

soul will merge with the Creator. This, the aim of human life, is a cause for joy not sorrow. This same sense of joyful celebration of the death of holy men is common in the Middle East. The day that the great Sufi saint Rumi died is celebrated every year with the joy of a wedding feast; as it was the experience of those present at his funeral that his soul was wedded to the Creator; hence his life is the example for all to follow.

However, we can see what a clever man Saul was with words and new ideas. We should remember that Saul was not only a Jew, he was also a Roman citizen. For this reason, much later, the Roman Emperors had no problem in taking on the belief system of those who called themselves followers of Saul's sect. Eventually forcing all Europeans to accept that these ideas are what true religion is all about, since they were originated by a Roman citizen. No doubt their idea was also to get people to be morally obedient.

Yet the man who started this idea was himself a man who needed to remove the beam from his own eye before he attempted to remove the mote from the eyes of others. i.e. he was not a qualified spiritual teacher.

Saul Confirms he is not a Qualified Teacher

Isha was very clear when he expressed the same concept in Matt. 7:3-5 (see below), which is stated throughout the Vedanta tradition, here quoted from a Divine teacher who lived in India in the 20th century :-

"The characteristics of the true teacher is that no trace of desire for the material life remains in him. He is the one from whom you can be sure you will get true direction to reach the spiritual goal. He is also possessed of all learning and knowledge in the scriptures and has applied the teaching in them; and through knowing their secrets has met with *Bhagavān* (the Creator) in himself. Where these attributes are found together, such a person truly carries the title of teacher."³²

This was the subject that Isha was teaching when he said :-

"And why beholdest thou the mote that is in thy brother's eye, but considerest not the beam that is in thine own eye?

"Or how wilt thou say to thy brother, let me pull out the mote out of thine eye; and behold a beam is in thine own eye.

"Thou hypocrite, first cast out the beam out of thine own eye; and then shalt thou see clearly to cast out the mote out of thy brother's eye." Matt. 7: 3 to 5.

It is clear that Isha is saying that a person should discover the goal of human life first before making any attempt to point others in the right direction. Saul had not gone through the process of realising God in his own life and was therefore not qualified to teach others about the spiritual subject. How is this

³² From the book "The Life and Teachings of His Divinity Shri Guru Deva" : ISBN 978-0-9571665-3-0

clear? Because when a person has realised the Creator in their life then, if they speak at all, they will carry universal wisdom in their speech.

"A false teacher is like a farmer who is ready with the plough to till the soil but has no seed to sow; even though the seeker's mind is ready to have seed planted into it. Knowledge of the scriptures is in itself not sufficient for giving true guidance. This leads to the teacher only guessing the answers to the seeker's questions. The one who knows the truth in himself, alone is able to give very precise answers to the doubts of his followers. The appearance of the good fruit of knowledge is a sign that the teacher is truly wise."³³ Shri Guru Deva

Certain statements and claims are not the language of a Self-realised soul. Such statements reveal the inner development of a person which cannot always be seen even by looking at them or being in their presence. Isha said :-

"But in vain do they worship me, teaching for doctrines to commandments of men. (i.e. seeking to control others.)

"Not that which goeth into the mouth defileth a man; but that which cometh out of the mouth, this defileth a man." Matt. 15: 9 & 11

This is the subject he was pointing us towards; meaning the recognition of who was a suitable teacher through his speech; so that we could be sure to get good teaching. But Saul said :-

"Because the foolishness of God is wiser than men; and the weakness of God is stronger than men." 1 Cor. 1:25

If Saul was trying to make a point about the nature of the Creator, he has chosen words which no man would use, who had realised the Truth in his life. To mention the words "foolishness" and "weakness" in connection with any description of the Creator has never been done by any Self-realised teacher in history. There are implications here about the Creator which should never be planted into anyone's mind when thinking of Him.

"That I have great heaviness and continual sorrow in my heart." Rom. 9:2

Such a statement could never be made by a man who had realised his own unity with the Creator. His life would be filled with joy and positiveness.

We are warned in the Yoga Vasishtha about following false teachers.

"Do not be led astray by the long-winded empty statements of the wicked self-appointed teachers who have no direct experience." V:29

Reviewing Saul's position; starting off as the persecutor of the followers of Isha, on his way into Damascus he unexpectedly met Isha, who was on his way out. The sense of sight, which we all treasure, was taken from him by a power which he had never before encountered; his first personal experience of what

³³ From the book "The Life and Teachings of His Divinity Shri Guru Deva" : ISBN 978-0-9571665-3-0

miraculous powers can do. What would he now do to be able to live after that? Sit by the roadside and beg for a living, as any blind person would do in those days. Such a prospect was horrifying to such a man as Saul.

Then he is visited by Ananias. Who knew all that had been going on by a form of telepathic communication between himself and Isha. Saul knew then that he was dealing with a man who had powers which he could not possibly understand. This perhaps was the first recorded real example of the fear of Christ. Then Ananias displays similar powers which Isha had. More reason for Saul to fear. How could he then continue his regime of persecution? People who had powers which could put a complete stop to anything which he might have done, powers which he did not understand.

Any intelligent and reasonable person, who's main agenda was self-preservation, would only do one thing; change the game plan completely. But he was really only an opportunist, charismatic cult leader. He saw then the chance to use his change of plan to his own advantage and claim that he had converted to become a follower of Isha. This was as a result of his encounter with the extraordinary powers of Isha and his followers. But he only promoted his own ideas. Where, in Saul's letters, is the teaching of Isha? Where are any of the parables? Where any mention of Isha's miracles? What we really have is a clear example of what Isha himself clearly predicted. I make no excuse for repeating these words. They are key to this subject.

"Many will say to me in that day, Lord, Lord, have we not prophesied in thy name? and in thy name have cast out devils? and in thy name done many wonderful works?

"And then will I profess unto them, 'I never knew you; depart from me, ye that work iniquity.'" Matt. 7: 22 & 23.

Summary of Saul's Position in History

We can easily trace the current basic idea which surrounds the belief system called Christianity through the above evidence readily available in the New Testament and in historic records.

After the execution attempt, Isha (Jesus) finally left Galilee and later, as he was leaving Damascus, he was confronted by Saul. In order to protect his situation and that of his company in a non-violent way, using one of his *siddhi* powers, he took Saul's sight away. Saul, who had long wanted to begin a Jewish sect or cult of his own, saw the opportunity which came from this event, to use the power of Isha and a made up story to support his new religious career.

Being strongly Jewish from childhood, Saul could not really break too far from the basic Jewish ideas in forming his new sect. He did not really know much of Isha's teaching but he was a well read theologian, so there is no doubt that he was capable of giving sound Jewish religious advice and reminders to

anyone. This he often does in his epistles; this does not make his religious comments the teachings of Isha; they are mainly Jewish.

He did not seem to agree with the annual Jewish business of being freed from sin through the ceremony of sacrificing the blood of a goat or calf. Although he was convinced that he could use the Jews' belief in this idea to create a new way of dealing with sin. Either he had the experience that this ritual did not work for him or he noticed that the Jews were tired of doing this every year with little or no effect on their lives becoming purer. Hence he thought to create a theory that all sin could be got rid of once and for all. So he invented the idea that this could happen by theoretically making Isha into a once-time sacrificial offering.

This allowed all those who had enough faith in this new idea, to believe that they were once and for all completely absolved of all their past iniquities. But in case this once again showed little change in the daily experience of life, he made it into a promise for the future i.e. redemption at death. This was entirely Saul's idea; but only an idea. It has no spiritual basis for it in any previous belief system. None of this was anything to do with the teachings of Isha. An idea only; maybe a good one, but one which does not really work, other than to give people a sense of relief that they are saved from sin, when really they are not. Also it is clear he did not believe it himself, which is proof that he only made it up as a theory and for 'sales talk'.

Saul's new faith idea caught on with the more gullible types through his charisma and his own method of convincing people, who really had little understanding of how sin could be dealt with or even what it really was. Hence many thousands of people from all belief backgrounds joined up with his new faith, with this quick redemption idea from Saul's 'sales talk' as a promise for the future. He underpins the whole idea with the power behind the name of Jesus Christ, but not with the teachings of Jesus (Isha). He makes it clear that it is based on his own gospel not that of Isha. In modern times such a sect would be called a cult. The intelligent Jews ignored him and continued to keep Judaism alive to the present day.

During the intervening centuries this new faith or cult grows in numbers and various sects develop; all with their own ideas and interpretations. It begins to interface with the politics of the Roman Emperors and is either accepted or rejected by them, depending on the fancy of the particular Emperor of the time. Some were for it, some were against. Remember, Roman Emperors were considered to be God; hence they were 'infallible'.

In the fourth century the Roman Emperor Constantine was having trouble with the various factions of the empire which included Italy, Greece, Anatolia, Syria and other parts of Europe and the Middle East. He had united the squabbling sections of the empire by slaughtering all opposition to his own rule. Some of the strife between the different nations and factions of the empire was

connected with their various belief systems, of which there were many. So he decided to make one belief system to cover the whole Roman Empire and make everyone follow it by decree. This was with the aim of uniting the Empire under one religion and putting a stop to the religious troubles. All this is recorded history of the Roman Empire. This took away the right which people had of following a belief system of their ancestors, which many tribes had done for centuries.

Thus the concept in Europe of a single religion or cult controlled by the state was introduced, possibly for the first time in European history. An idea later taken up by Islam. The way the new Christian faith was administered was much along the lines of Saul of Tarsus and his idea of a belief system. This became a fundamental divergence from that which Isha taught. Isha was quite clear that his way to approach the Father was for the individual to approach him alone :-

"But thou when thou prayest, enter into thy closet, and when thou hast shut thy door, pray to thy Father, which is in secret; and thy Father which seeth in secret shall reward thee openly." Matt. 6:6

As a state belief system with a one-size-fits-all approach the individual cannot then know of Isha's concept of a personal approach to the Father.

This took the faith into a socio-political subject as a way to bring in social controls of the people and therefore less of a spiritual way to God. Then it was that any remaining way of following the teachings of Isha died a death under the Nicæan Creed. Their idea was that believers had access to the Creator only through the Emperor and his bishops; which is very cult-like. Isha said many times that followers could have a personal relationship with the Creator. Under the new state religion they were not permitted to think in that way; another feature of modern day cults; a communal approach rather than an individual way to God.

So as to stamp this idea onto the people a book was required; hence Constantine gathered various scribes, editors and theologians together to make up a scripture (the Bible) which would include all the main belief systems which were spread across the Empire. Being Emperor, he had the contacts and resources to do this. For this he included a lot of the old Jewish books so as to satisfy the influential Jewish sects. He also included some of the writings used by those groups who followed the teachings of Isha (the four gospels). These people would have called themselves Christian; there were previously many sects. Also he included the writings (the Epistles) used by those who followed the various ideas of Saul's sect, which were called Christian Jews and were probably also using the Jewish scriptures. Then he included a few other epistles along with the book of Revelation. All minor beliefs without written down faith ideas were eliminated or side-lined. There were at least a dozen of these.

There is no other way to understand how such disparate scriptures, which really have nothing to do with each other, were all put into one book called the Holy Bible. All these were edited so that the Roman style of life, such as meat eating and non belief (or non-understanding) of reincarnation, would not cause any issues or necessitate big changes in life style. This was necessary, as all Roman citizens would have to become Christian as well and they would not be happy to change their lifetime habits.

All available original scripts were then destroyed or hidden away, as none apparently existed until the Nag Hamadi and other finds came to light in recent times. To set his new system rolling, Constantine announced that he was converting to Christianity from having been a Roman Pagan. This change he only did superficially. Major dates of religious celebration were all linked to the previous Pagan times of the year. The whole format of the new faith was based on existing Roman practice. The buildings, festivals, rituals, dress, sacraments, saints, gods and doctrine were all transferred to the new belief; along with ideas of resurrection, blood sacrifice, bread and wine and marriage ceremonies which were all existing ideas transferred to the new faith.

This new belief system was consolidated with the very first council in Nicaea where the now well known creed was put forward as an obligatory way of following Constantine's new faith idea. Death or banishment followed for those who refused. All of this was far from the ideas of Isha. If we are honest, it is difficult to call this new idea of a cult converted into a state controlled belief system, a true religion. The scriptures put together are all from different backgrounds and different traditions. The whole book is therefore filled with contradictions and food for future controversy. It is not a truly inspired coherent scripture, no matter what anyone says. Yet there are some powerful spiritual concepts contained within it. These verses of good teaching scattered throughout it are its only real spiritual merit.

Many centuries of change and mutation of Constantine's basic system have simply drifted further and further from the message of Isha. Yet much of the power in Isha's remaining teaching is still partially effective for those who take it on in their lives and try to become purified through living by it. This effectiveness, if we can truly see it, comes to the devout individual from Isha himself; when he sees that a person's heart, individually truly loves him for what he is. In the same way this book has arrived in this 21st century.

Hence we can say the long lie started with Saul when he fulfilled his wish of starting a new Jewish sect or cult. The real power and beauty of Isha's teaching has been weakened, mutilated and wrongly interpreted. Yet many have seen through this and have gained benefit.

Conclusion

So from Saul's own evidence, not intended by him to have been read by us, we can surely conclude that the road to Damascus event was not conversion, but a change of plan it certainly was. The first Christian cult was started in that first Christian century. And we need to answer the question; what was the purpose of Emperor Constantine including the letters of Saul (Paul) into a book of religious teachings? Was it to undermine the authority of the Christians (i.e. to show the disarray they were in) or was it to promote the words of a Roman citizen, as if they were holy scripture?

Perhaps we will never know the answer. But one thing is certain; Saul of Tarsus was only interested in personal fame and promoting his own ideas, not those of Isha but his own, packaged with the name of Isha. It is exactly what Isha meant when he said they will teach "in my name". Because he knew that when a person says that, then it will be weak teaching; simply because a true and competent teacher does not teach in the name of another teacher, other than to reinforce knowledge based on Truth with equivalent teaching.

In all this material here about the history of Saul's sect, I do not say that any part is right or wrong; good or bad. I have only attempted to open up the facts for my readers to see it for themselves in a new light.

Yet we should not leave out the vision that all this was the plan of the Creator Himself, since in this world there is truly nothing but Him. He knows that normal human beings are basically self-centred; He can use this trait to spread some aspects of the Eternal System of Righteousness in any way He wishes. All this, so that some wisdom from that Eternal System would find its way into the minds of Europeans. Creating an event which we cannot find very much historical precedent for. So all is not lost when the Will of *Bhagavān* makes a move to lift the world from the ingrained ignorance of this dark age called the *Kali Yuga*. This is how to see part of the power and purpose in Isha's life. In this way we should understand that he can instigate a further stage in that injection of the Eternal System into western thinking any time he wishes.

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